

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE

GRADUATE PROGRAM

**INFLUENCE OF SOWING DATE AND NUMBER OF VINE ON GROWTH, YIELD AND
QUALITY OF WATERMELON (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) AT KOGA IRRIGATION SCHEME,
WEST GOJJAM ZONE, ETHIOPIA**

M.Sc. Thesis

By

Yibeltal Tilahun

February, 2023

Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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By

Yibeltal Tilahun Ayele

**Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of Master of Science
(M.Sc.) in "Horticulture"**

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THESIS APPROVAL SHEET

As member of the Board of Examiners of the Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) thesis open defence examination, we have read and evaluated this thesis prepared by **Mr Yibeltal Tilahun Ayele** entitled “**Influence of Sowing Date and Number of Vine on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) at Koga Irrigation Scheme, West Gojjam Zone, Ethiopia**”. We here by certify that, the thesis is accepted for fulfilling the requirements of the award of the degree of Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) in "**Horticulture**".

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that, this thesis entitled “**Influence of Sowing Date and Number of Vine on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) at Koga Irrigation Scheme, West Gojjam Zone, Ethiopia**” submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) in “**Horticulture**” to the Graduate Program of College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University by Mr **Yibeltal Tilahun (ID No. BDU1300815)** is an authentic work carried out by him under our guidance. This thesis has not been submitted to any other institution anywhere for the award of any academic degree, diploma, or certificate to the best of our knowledge.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my mother Mrs Birhan Nega.

ABBREVIATION/ACRONYMS

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CIMMYT	International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center
CSA	Central Statistical Authority
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FAOSTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization Statistics Database
Kg /ha	Kilogram per hectare
MRR	Marginal Rate of Return
NIHORT	National Horticultural Research Institute
RCBD	Random Complete Block Design
SAS	Software Analysis System
TSS	Total Soluble Solid

**INFLUENCE OF PLANTING DATE AND NUMBER OF VINE ON GROWTH, YIELD
AND QUALITY OF WATERMELON (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) AT KOGA IRRIGATION
SCHEME, WEST GOJJAM ZONE, ETHIOPIA**

By Yibeltal Tilahun

Major Advisor: Dr. Melkamu Alemayehu

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ABSTARACT

Koga Irrigation Scheme is one of the potential watermelon producing areas in Ethiopia. However, the average yield of watermelon is low due to inappropriate sowing date and poor agronomic practice like vine pruning. Therefore, a field experiment was carried out during the 2021/22 irrigation season to evaluate the influences of sowing date and number of vine on growth, yield and quality of watermelon at Koga irrigation scheme, North Mecha Woreda, West Gojjam Zone, Ethiopia. The experiment consisted of three sowing dates (D_1 : November 12, D_2 : December 12 and D_3 : January 12) and four level of vine per plant (VP_1 : without pruning, VP_2 : 2 vines, VP_3 : 3 vines, and VP_4 : 4 vines arranged with factorial combination in Random Complete Block Design with three replications. Data on phenology, growth, yield and physico-chemical quality attributes were collected and analysed using Statistical Analysis Software (SAS) version 9.4. The results clearly showed that 50% flowering, maturity, number of lateral branch per vine, leaf area, vine length, fruit size classification, fruit per vine and per plant, marketable, unmarketable and total fruit yields, and total soluble solids were influenced by date of sowing and number of vines per plant. The interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine influenced number of lateral branch per vine, number of fruit per plant, unmarketable yield and, fruit size category. Moreover, significantly highest marketable tuber yield of watermelon was obtained from plants sown at January and plants with three vines per plant with the values of 45.7 t ha^{-1}) and 42.15 t ha^{-1} , respectively. Based on the partial budget analysis, watermelon sown at January combined with three vines gave the highest net benefit ($1,121,616.00 \text{ Birr ha}^{-1}$) and marginal rate of returns (1,944%). Based on the results of the present study, sowing of watermelon in the month January and maintaining three vines per plants recorded the highest marketable yield and better fruit quality of watermelon, which can be recommended for economical production of the crop in the study area and areas with similar agro ecologies. As the study is limited to one season and location, further investigation over seasons and locations is also recommended.

Key words: Crimson Sweet variety, fruit quality, sowing date, vine pruning

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Justification

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae and is widely cultivated crop in the world (Dauda *et al.*, 2008). There are over 1,200 varieties of watermelon worldwide (Gichimu *et al.*, 2008). Three types of watermelon are grown in drier regions of Africa: the dessert type (*C. lanatus* var. *lanatus* L), the cooking type [*C. lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakai var *citroides*] and the seed type (*C. colocynthis* L. Schrad.). (Bahari *et al.*, 2012; Gbotto *et al.*, 2016; Leskovar *et al.*, 2004). Three-fourth of the world's watermelon yield is produced in Asia, with China being the leading producer (FAO, 2019). According to FAO (2019), the top five watermelon producing countries in the world are China, Iran, Turkey, Brazil, and Uzbekistan with the production estimate of 79,276,300 tons (42.88 t ha⁻¹), 4,059,786 tons (29.81 t ha⁻¹), 4,011,313 tons (41.99 t ha⁻¹), 2,314,700 tons (22.00 t ha⁻¹), and 2,030,992 tons (39.81 t ha⁻¹), respectively. The total world production in the same year was 118,413,465 tons, which was produced on 3,477,285 ha of land with an average productivity of 34 t ha⁻¹. Algeria is the leading watermelon producing country in Africa followed by Egypt and Morocco (FAO, 2019). Watermelon was introduced in East Shoa Zone of Oromia region which is the dominant production area in Ethiopia. However, there is no official report on the average productivity of the crop in Ethiopia (Fanos Mekonnen, 2014). The average productivity of watermelon at North *Mecha Woreda* was about 10 t ha⁻¹ (MoA, 2019 unpublished).

Watermelon has high water content and also delivers many other important nutrients, including lycopene and vitamin C (Mandel *et al.*, 2005). Watermelon is a highly relished fruit for salad preparation all over the world due to its highly nutritive value. It is also reported that watermelon seeds are used as a food source (Loukou *et al.*, 2007). The fruit also contains vitamin C and A in form of the disease fighting beta-carotene, Lycopene and beta-carotene compounds which are not found in vitamin/mineral supplements (Maynard, 2001). Potassium is also available in the fruit, which is believed to help in the control of blood pressure and prevention of heart attack. Watermelon fruit contains about 6% sugar and 91% water by weight. As with many other fruits, it is a source of vitamin C and amino acid called citrulline (Mandel *et al.*, 2005).

Watermelon requires warm climate and relatively long growing season (Maynard, 2001; Charles, 2005). Watermelon seeds germinate well and plants thrive at 25°C - 30°C. Fruits mature best at 30 °C. Continuous rain or cloudy day will not only stunt the plant growth but also reduce the flowering and fruit setting. If watermelons mature in rainy season, the sugar content will be significantly reduced. Watermelon grows best on sandy loam soils with good drainage and slightly acidic pH (Paris, 2015). The optimum soil pH and annual rainfall for watermelon is from 6.0-6.8 and 400-600 mm respectively. The crop grows in diverse ecologies with altitudes below 1,500m.a.s.l (Ke *et al.*, 2012; Suchoff *et al.*, 2019).

Three different types of watermelon namely dessert types, seed types and cooking types are grown by farmers (Maggs-Kölling *et al.*, 2000). Date of sowing and management activities like pruning and trainings are influenced the growth and yield of watermelon. For instance, a report by Bellad and Umesh (2018) revealed that a highly significance difference in growth parameters like vine length and number of lateral branches per vine was observed between the sowing time of January and November. The same authors reported that the highest and lowest number in vine length and number of lateral branches per vine are observed from the sowing time of January and November, respectively. Similarly, Merwade (2000) and Ravikumar *et al.* (2005) indicated that the flowering behavior of vines sown during November months performed poorly compared to January and February sowing.

Pruning is a special horticultural practice that is carried out by removing some parts of plant to boost flowering and subsequent fruiting. The main purpose of pruning is to promote the balance between vegetative growth and fruit load (Anwar *et al.*, 2019). Pruning improves yield and fruit size as well as helps to synchronize harvesting period (Oga and Umekwe, 2016). Oga and Umekwe (2016) indicated that the pruned watermelon plants produced the longest vine, number of leaves, number of flowers and number of fruits. Pruning has been reported to increase yield of cucumber (Nayak *et al.*, 2018). Vine pruning of watermelon also is important to enhance mechanical harvesting, the production of hybrid seed, ease of control of insect pests and diseases. However, excessive pruning on the other hand significantly influence the growth, yield and population of plants as reported by different scholars (Gusmini and Wehner, 2005). It is thus paramount to evaluate the effects of pruning and sowing date on the performance of watermelon.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Watermelon is important for a source of nutrients like lycopene, vitamin C and A, besides to being source of income for smallholder farmers (Mandel *et al.*, 2005). Despite the importance of the crop and suitability of the country for watermelon production, its production is not well distributed. Moreover, watermelon productivity is low as compared to the world and other African countries. Although there is no official report on the average productivity of the crop in Ethiopia, the average yield harvested by the farmers in the study area, is very low as compared with the world average productivity. This might be due to many constraints such as inappropriate use of sowing date (Susila *et al.*, 2012), acidic problems in the scheme (Dires Tewabe *et al.*, 2020), inappropriate use of management activity like pruning (Gichimu *et al.*, 2008; Oga and Umekwe, 2016), lack of adapted variety (Huitron-Ramirez *et al.*, 2009), Environmental factor (Amsalu Ayana, 2014; Kassa Ashebre, 2015), high cost of seeds, insufficient certified production inputs, lack of proper storage facilities, price fluctuations, limited access to affordable sources of financing, lack of extension services (Waweru *et al.*, 2019; Ddamulira *et al.*, 2021), non-controllable factors (like frost, disease and insect pests) and improper use postharvest handling practices (Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.*, 2015) are the most important once. Among those date of sowing and agronomic practices like pruning and trainings are the major watermelon production problems in Ethiopia as well as the study area.

The production of watermelon is a new vendor in Amhara Region. Farmers at Koga Irrigation Scheme started to produce the crop in the last 5-7 years. Most of Koga Irrigation farmers sow watermelon seeds in December by using traditional management activities. The farmer didn't know exact date of sowing and management activities like pruning and training. Farmers produce watermelon fruit without pruning and fertilization. Limited studies were conducted so far in Ethiopia including the study area on different aspects of the crop.

In the production of watermelon, dates of sowings are a major problem said by watermelon growing farmers. On the other hand, the number of vines per plant is an important parameter that determines the performance of *Cucurbitaceae* family including watermelon (Gomes *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, to tackle the above problems this research was initiated with the aim of identifying the appropriate date of sowing and number of vines for increased growth, yield and quality of watermelon fruits in the North *Mecha Woreda*.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

1.3.1. General objective

The general objective of the present study was to contributing for the improvement of production and productivity of watermelon by determining the optimum sowing date and number of vines per plant in the study area.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

- To evaluate the effects of sowing date and number of vine on growth, yield and quality of watermelon in the study area
- To identify the optimum sowing date and number of vines for economical production of watermelon in the study area.

CHAPTER 2: LITRATURE REVIEW

2.1. Origin, Distribution and Botany of Watermelon

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) belongs to the family *Cucurbitaceae* (Schippers, 2000) with its center of origin traced to the Kalahari and Sahara deserts in Africa (Mayberry *et al.*, 2008). Three types of watermelon are grown in drier regions of Africa: the dessert type (*C. lanatus* var. *lanatus* L), the cooking type *C. lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakaivarcitroides] and the seed type (*C. colocynthis* L. Schrad.). Dessert watermelon is grown worldwide, has a characteristic sweet taste, a low-calorie fruit used mostly in salads and juices (Bahari *et al.*, 2012; Gbotto *et al.*, 2016; Leskovar *et al.*, 2004). The cooking type, also called cow watermelon, is normally used as animal feed, for cooking thick porridge, or mixed in dry maize (*Zea mays* L.) grain (Mujaju *et al.*, 2011). The seed type watermelon is mostly grown in Central to West Africa and is used to extract oil, make egusi soup, snacks, and flour (Nantoume *et al.*, 2012).

Watermelon spread from Africa to Asia about 800 A.D and to Europe in 961 A.D. The crop was subsequently brought to America by Europeans in the 17th Century (Wehner, 2008). Modern watermelon breeding has mainly taken place in the USA, from where many of the well-known varieties originate. However, China and other parts of the Far East have been also played an important role in breeding of cultivated species of watermelon (Wehner, 2008). In Africa, watermelon cultivation has considerably increased in the last one decade with the major production areas located in the Sahel, Sudan and Guinea agro-ecological zones. In recent times, its cultivation has stretched down to the forest belts of south western Nigeria (NIHORT, 2000).

According to Boualem *et al.* (2016) formation of watermelon root system begins prior to emergence of cotyledons to the soil surface and reaches maximum extension by the time of flowering. Watermelon features a highly branching taproot extending up to 1m deep into the soil. Some 15 or more lateral root branches are obtained from the main root. The stem is a long, trailing vine reaching 5 m and more in length, highly branched; forming secondary side shoots which, in turn, branch out. The vines, especially the younger shoots, are covered with long, woolly hairs protecting the plant from overheating (Dube *et al.*, 2021). Watermelon leaves are dark green, with prominent veins. They have three large lobes, each further divided into smaller lobes. Watermelon leaves are heart shaped with three to seven lobes per leaf and

are produced on trailing vines (Davis *et al.*, 2008). Watermelon flowers are yellow having five petals, about 1 cm in diameter. Watermelon vines like squash, pumpkin and cucumber have separate male and female flowers on the same plant. Plants are monoecious with yellow flowers that are approximately 3 cm in diameter (Boualem *et al.*, 2016).

Watermelon is mostly grown for its fruit. The fruit weight of most commercially available watermelons ranges from 3 to 13 kg (Maynard, 2001; Wehner, 2008). Fruit shape is often spherical but can be globular, oval or oblong. The watermelon rind consists of two layers. The thin, glossy outer layer, or exocarp, is typically boldly striped or otherwise patterned in two shades of green. The green colours can range from light to dark, and the stripes are jaggedly edged and range in breadth from very narrow to very broad. The thick inner layer of the rind, or mesocarp, is wet, white and hard. Underneath the rind is the watery fruit flesh or endocarp, the portion of the fruit that is usually eaten. Early in the development, the fruit flesh is hard, white or otherwise pale-coloured, and insipid. In citron watermelons, the fruit flesh remains hard, nearly colourless and tasteless to fruit maturity (Xu *et al.*, 2012). In sweet dessert watermelons, the flesh of the maturing fruit becomes tender and accumulates carotenoid pigments and sucrose (Elmstrom and Davis, 1981; Brown and Summers, 1985; Soteriou *et al.*, 2014). Colour begins to accumulate between 2 and 3 weeks after anthesis, first around the developing seeds and thereafter gradually spreading throughout the endocarp (Perkins-Veazie *et al.*, 2012). Depending on the genotype, the flesh of ripe watermelon fruits can range in colour from red to pink, orange, yellow, a mixture of these colours, green and white (Gusmini and Wehner, 2006).

2.2. Watermelon Production in Ethiopia

Ethiopia has diverse agro-ecologies, which are associated with a great variation in altitude ranging from below sea level up to 4620 meters above sea level (Kassa Ashebre, 2015). These variations make the country suitable for the production of temperate, tropical and sub-tropical fruits and vegetables (Amsalu Ayana *et al.*, 2014). Ethiopian farmers use a range of production methods, which demonstrate the diversity under which the crop is grown and different niches the crop occupies in farmer livelihood. Smallholder farmers grow most watermelons for consumption (Melese Asfaw, 2022). Watermelon was introduced in East Shoa Zone of Oromia region which is currently the dominant place where it is produced in Ethiopia (Fanos Mekonnen, 2014). Quality and yield are the main factors influencing

watermelon production in Ethiopia. The quality of watermelons produced in Ethiopia tends to be low compared to elsewhere. According to tests at farm gate, road side markets and supermarkets, its average total soluble solids (TSS) content was found to be less than 6% Brix; the minimum TSS should not be lower than 9% Brix world standard (Fanos Mekonnen, 2014). The productivity of watermelon is generally low due to lack of awareness of producers about agronomic practices, time of harvest, and variety types. All producers sell through the process of “*terega*” which means buyers collect all watermelons at the same time. Mature and immature watermelons are all harvested together, resulting in low quality of the produce (Fanos Mekonnen, 2014).

Some watermelon producers have received extension services on watermelon production techniques and marketing from the government or NGOs in Ethiopia. NGOs give important information’s to the farmers in terms of introducing adaptable varieties that produce good fruits, providing technical and practical training on production techniques supported by demonstration and establishment and strengthening of sustainable input supply and marketing linkages (Fanos Mekonnen, 2014). There are various watermelon varieties grown worldwide. In Ethiopia, common watermelons varieties have been grown in different Regions are Sugar Baby, Sukari F1, Crimson Sweet, Sweet Rose and Charleston Gray (Melese Asfaw, 2022).

2.3. Opportunities and Challenges of Watermelon Production in Ethiopia

Watermelon is produced with minimal fertilizer and pesticide inputs in Africa including Ethiopia is usually grown as an intercrop; thus, it is not considered a priority when allocating land for agricultural production. This implies that some pests, though not of great concern in other production systems, are of significance in Africa (Dube *et al.*, 2020).

Watermelons have evolved several gene expression patterns, biochemical pathways and physiological mechanisms not present in most crops that allow them to adapt to drought and high light stress (Nanasato *et al.*, 2010). Ethiopia has ideal temperatures, long warm growing seasons, and soils for commercial watermelon production. Watermelons grow best on sandy loam soils, with good drainage and which are slightly acid pH (Anonymous, 2011). As countries in Africa are often affected by drought, adapted watermelon cultivars are ideal given they require minimum moisture and have high returns on the market compared to other drought hardy crops. Watermelon growth is more rapid during the dry season (under

irrigation) than during the wet season (rainfall period) due to erratic precipitation patterns (Mtumtum, 2012). Excess water during maturity can cause fruits to crack which reduces yield and fruit quality (Davis *et al.*, 2018).

In Ethiopia, like other African countries, watermelon cultivation is prevalent in drought-prone, semi-arid, areas with an annual rainfall below 650 mm. Most watermelon landraces provide important traits for drought and heat tolerance, such as higher biomass, which would greatly improve crop adaptation to climate change worldwide (Said and Fatiha, 2018). Watermelon cultivation has not had a high level of technological improvement such as use of new hybrids, fertilizer, and processing in Ethiopia compared to other crops (Kahan, 2013).

Little research on watermelon production has been done in Africa including Ethiopia compared to cereals and legumes (Davis *et al.*, 2008). Fruit quality is an important attribute in the production of watermelons for a specific market (Kuvare, 2005). Generally, the market prefers red as opposed to yellow-fleshed fruit primarily due to lack of yellow fleshed cultivars with high-quality fruit and consumer resistance. Other cultivars are prone to physiological problems such as cracking, hollow heart, mealy textures, or a lack of uniformity in fruit shape (Chogou *et al.*, 2019). The most important watermelon pests are leaf-chewing beetles and sucking insects, which damage leaves, flowers, and root-knot nematodes that affect water and nutrient uptake (Alao, 2016). Diseases of economic importance include mildew, fusarium wilt, mosaic viruses, and bacterial rind necrosis (Said and Fatiha, 2018). It is important to note that watermelon is produced with minimal fertilizer and pesticide inputs in Africa as well as Ethiopia and is usually grown as an intercrop; thus, it is not considered a priority when allocating land for agricultural production. This implies that some pests, though not of great concern in other production systems, are of significance in Ethiopia (Asfaw Melese, 2022).

2.4. Effect of Date of Sowing on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon

Sowing date influences growth, yield and quality of watermelon (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007; and Bellad and Umesh, 2018). It is because sowing date influences the extent of temperature and length of growing season that in turn influences growth, yield and quality of watermelon (Mitumtum, 2012 and Chandrashekhhar 2008). In this regard, Bellad and Umesh (2018) and Balkaya and Odabas (2007) reported that phenological parameters like flowering, fruit set and maturity dates were earlier in watermelon sowed at month January than November and December. Date of sowing also influences days to male and female flower initiation and sex ratio. Additionally, Bellad and Umesh (2018), the longest period for initiation of male and female flowers was recorded at November sowing while January sowing recorded the shortest period for initiation of male and female flowers. The vines sown during November months performed poorly with respect to flowering behavior compared to January and February sowing (Merwade, 2000; Ravikumar *et al.*, 2005). Similarly, Mtumtum (2012) stated that watermelon growth is more rapid during the dry season than during the wet season.

The growth and development of the watermelon plants are also influenced by the date of sowing. (Bellad and Umesh, 2018) reported that the Growth parameters like the leaf area, vine length and number of lateral branches per vine are significantly more on plants sown in the month January while November sowing recorded less leaf area, vine length and lateral branches (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007). Bellad and Umesh (2018) reported that January sowing recorded the highest number of fruits per vine, fresh fruit yield per vine, fruit per plant, marketable and unmarketable yield, number of seeds per fruit, seed weight per fruit, percentage of filled seeds, seed yield per hectare. On the other hand, all these yield components were significantly lowest in Novembers sowing. Similarly, November sowing recorded the lowest seed yield per vine and hectare compared to January sowing as reported by other scholars (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007; Chandrashekhhar, 2008). Additionally, the accumulation of dry matter reached its highest peak under full sun (Pereira *et al.*, 2011), which is the case in January sowing compared to November. Generally, sowing in the month January recorded better growth, yield and quality of watermelon (Blkaya and Odabas, 2007; Bellad and Umesh, 2018; Mitumtum, 2012).

Both physical and quality parameters are also influenced by sowing date. Sowing in the month January recorded highest average fruit weight, specific gravity, fruit width and fruit rind thicknesses compared to sowing in the month November (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007, Mitumtum, 2012).. Similarly, total soluble solid, juice content and juice pH of watermelon were significantly influenced by sowing date as reported by different researchers (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007, Chandrashekhar, 2008, Bellad and Umesh, 2018).

2.5. Effects of Number of Vine on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon

Pruning is a special horticultural practice that is carried out by removing some parts of plant to boost flowering and subsequent fruiting. The main purpose of pruning is to promote the balance between vegetative growth and fruit load (Anwar *et al.*, 2019). Pruning improves yield and fruit size as well as helps to synchronize harvesting period (Oga and Umekwe, 2016). Researches that were conducted in different parts of the world showed that pruning influences the growth, yield and quality of watermelon. In this regard, Gholipouri and Nazarnejad (2007) reported that vine-pruned watermelon plants extend the time for fruit maturity and ripening, which is associated with the increase in fruit number per plant, which require more time for dry matter accumulation and maturity. Phenological parameters like flowering, fruit setting, and fruit maturity can be also influenced by density of watermelon plants. According to Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021), these phenological parameters were occurred at earlier days at highest population densities (un-pruned) compared to lowest density, which can be comparable with un-pruned and pruned plants, respectively. Similarly, pruned watermelon plants produced the longest vine, highest leaf area and highest number of leaves, flowers and fruits (Oga and Umekwe, 2016).

Pinching at the node increased number of branches per plant of *Cucurbita moschata* (Eve *et al.*, 2016) and number of fruits, yield per vine and yield per hectare of cucumber (Nayak *et al.*, 2018). The authors also reported that pinching (reducing number of stem) recorded the tallest plants and highest number of leaves and number of branches per plant, which is in line with the results of Eve *et al.* (2016), and Oga and Umekwe (2016). Increased number of leaves and number of branches per plants due to pruning also lead to increased fruit number, and fruit yield per plants (Warren *et al.*, 1998, Dittmar *et al.*, 2006, Gichimu *et al.*, 2009). Warren *et al.* (1998) indicated that watermelon plants with many branches produce higher yields than those with few branches where un-pruned watermelon plants produce more

unmarketable fruits than pruned watermelon plants. This is probably associated with stiff competition of un-pruned branches for growth resources as indicated by Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021). According to the authors, highest number of vine per plant was recorded at the lowest plant density, whereas the lowest number of vine per plant was recorded at the highest plant population.

Warren *et al.* (1998) indicated that highest marketable fruit yield was recorded from pruned plants than the un-pruned plants, which is obviously associated with the research competition between plants. Similarly, Kermani *et al.* (2014) also reported that the highest fruit yield (142.2 t/ha) and seed yield (3219 kg/ha) of pumpkin were obtained from stem-pruned plants, which were pruned at early growth stage while un-pruned plants recorded the lowest fruit yield (112 ton/ha) and seed yield (2775 kg/ha). High input management practices in watermelon produce greater marketable yield, higher number of marketable fruit/plant and higher fruit weight than low input management practices (Kahan, 2013; Dube *et al.*, 2020). Good management practices improves yield, lycopene, and vitamin C levels (Davis *et al.*, 2008; Leskovar *et al.*, 2004). The reason is during stem pruning there is reduced the up taking of resource computation between stem (Warren *et al.*, 1998 Gusmini and Wehner, 2005). Additionally, Viana *et al.* (2008) reported that the lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume and plant vigour and finally the higher yield as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. The lower yield recorded on watermelon plants without pruning could result from competition for water, nutrients and light (Gomes *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, Munoz-Rengifo *et al.* (2018) argued that since watermelon has naturally many branches, pruning is advised to keep adequate number of branches, leaves and fruits to enable them to share efficiently the plant resources.

Pruning also influences the size distribution and chemical properties of watermelon fruits which is associated with reduction of competition for growth resources and shading effects. According to Pereira *et al.* (2011) accumulation of dry matter reached its highest peak under full sun. Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) also reported that the highest TSS was recorded with the lowest density which could be associated with the reduction of shading effect of the plants, which may contribute to high sugar content of watermelon fruits. In this regard, Watson (2002) observed an inverse relationship between sugar concentration and level of shading. Ford (2007) also reported that fruits harvested from watermelon plants with two vines had 18% more TSS than those fruits harvested from watermelon plants with four vines.

Sweetness in watermelon is associated to TSS (Maynard *et al.*, 2002; Cheng *et al.*, 2016) where sweetness is prerequisite for high quality of watermelon fruit (Park and Cho, 2012).

According to Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) most of the fruits obtained from the highest plant density were mini in size, which could be associated with competition among plants that can be managed by pruning. Because of higher price consumers having low incomes prefer small-to-medium-sized fruits (Zhou, 2011). Watermelon fruits around 3 kg are mostly preferred in the local markets (Tigist, 2016). Generally, fruits not more than 3.5 kg in weight are popular by consumers worldwide (Gusmini and Wehner, 2005, Walters *et al.*, 2012; Compagnol *et al.*, 2012, Nascimento *et al.*, 2018).

2.6. Interaction Effect of Sowing Date and Number of Vine on Growth, Yield and Quality of Watermelon

Growth and fruit yield of watermelons are influenced by the interaction effect of sowing date and stem pruning of watermelon which is observed by the findings of different researchers. According to Kermani *et al.* (2014) and Bellad and Umesh (2016) sowing date and stem pruning interacted to influence lateral branches and number of fruits per plant. According to the scholars number of lateral branches and fruits per plants were higher on plants sown at January and vine pruned plants. On the other hand, low number of branches and fruits were recorded on plants sown at November and un-pruned plants. Other research findings dissipated that phenological parameters including (days to 50 % of germination stand count at final harvest) were not significantly influenced by the interaction effect of sowing date and stem pruning (Ara *et al.*, 2007; Maboko *et al.*, 2011; Bellad and Umesh, 2018).

Similar to the growth parameters, yield and fruit size classification of watermelon are influenced by the interaction effect of sowing date and stem pruning of cucurbits which is observed by the findings of different researchers. In this regard, Bellad and Umesh (2018) have been observed highest number of fruits per plant and big sized fruits from plants that were sown at January. On the other hand plants, November sowing and un-pruning of cucurbit plants recorded the highest unmarketable yield compared to January sowing with pruning (Maboko *et al.*, 2011; Rafaella *et al.*, 2018; Kermani Poorbaghaiy *et al.* 2014).

CHAPTER 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted at *Koga* Irrigation Scheme, North *Mecha Woreda* of Amhara Region, Ethiopia during the 2021/2022 cropping season under irrigation condition. *Koga* Irrigation Scheme is found about 35 km far to southwest of the Amhara Regional State administrative city, Bahir Dar (Figure 3.1). *Koga* Irrigation Scheme is located at 11° 10'N to 11° 25'N latitude and 37° 02'E to 37° 17'E longitude with an elevation of 1960 m.a.s.l (Minwyelet Jemberie, 2017). The mean annual rainfall of *Koga* Irrigation Scheme is between 800 to 2,200 mm with a mean value of about 1,420 mm. The mean annual minimum and maximum temperatures are 9 °C and 32 °C, respectively (Abebaw Abiyu and Tena Alamirew, 2015). The soil type of *Koga* irrigation site is Nitisols with the dominant texture of clay and the soil has strongly acidic characteristics (Alebachew Enyew *et al.*, 2020).

Koga Irrigation Scheme is one of the irrigation schemes developed by the government of Ethiopia to enhance the production and productivity of horticultural crops in north-western Ethiopia. The irrigation scheme is about 7,000 ha large and mostly used for the production of command vegetables including onion, potato, tomato, pepper, cabbage, carrots and etc. by smallholder farmers using furrow irrigation system (Melkamu Alemayehu and Minwyelet Jemberie, 2018). Additionally, cereal crops like wheat, maize and etc. are also produced during the main rainy season in the scheme (Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 3.1: Study area map

Source: National Meteorology Agency, Bahir Dar (2021/22)

Figure 3.2 Maximum, minimum and mean temperature of the experimental site

3.2. Experimental Treatments and Design

The experiment consisted of three date of sowing November 12 (D1), December 12 (D2) and January 12 (D3) and number of vine (un-pruned, two vines, 3 vines, and 4 vines). It was arranged in 3x4 factorial combinations in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications.

3.3. Experimental Materials, Procedure and Management

“*Crimson Sweet*” variety of watermelon was used as a test crop. The total area of the experimental field was 26.6m*60.6m (1,611.96m²) as indicated in Figure 3.2. The plot was 7.2 m in length and had 4.5 m width with the gross plot area of 32.4m² (7.2x4.5 m) while the net plot area was 19.4m² (5.4x3.6m). The spaces between blocks were 2.5m and the spaces between plots along the replications were 0.6m. Total numbers of plots in the three replications were 36.

Table 3.1: Treatment combinations of the experiment

Sowing date	No of vines	Treatment combination	Treatment Code
November (D1)	Without pruning (VP1)	D1VP1	1
	Two vines (VP2)	D1VP2	2
	Three vines (VP3)	D1VP3	3
	Four vines (VP4)	D1VP4	4
December (D2)	Without pruning (VP1)	D2VP1	5
	Two vines (VP2)	D2VP2	6
	Three vines (VP3)	D2VP3	7
	Four vines (VP4)	D2VP4	8
January (D3)	Without pruning (VP1)	D3VP1	9
	Two vines (VP2)	D3VP2	10
	Three vines (VP3)	D3VP3	11
	Four vines (VP4)	D3VP4	12

Figure 3.3: Field layout of the experiment

The experimental site was ploughed to fine filth and leveled. Beds with the size of 7.2x4.5m and five ridges per plot were prepared. Seeds of Crimson“Sweet” variety of watermelon, which were bought from Green life seed company, were directly sown at the spacing of 1.8x0.9m between row and between plants within rows, respectively. By sowing two seeds of watermelon were sown in a hole based on the specified sowing date. After two weeks of sowing healthy and strong seedlings were left and the remaining weak seedlings were thinned (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022). There were four rows per plot while each row contained five watermelon plants.

The blanket recommended NPSZnB and Urea fertilizers at the rates of 100 kg ha⁻¹each were applied in the present study. NPSZnB fertilizer was applied at the time of sowing while urea was applied as split application where half of the quantity was applied at planting and the remaining half 45 days after planting. Plants were irrigated by furrow irrigation system at 7 days interval for the first four weeks then every 14 days till harvesting (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

Based on the treatment pruning of plants was started fourth weeks after planting where vines other that specified in the treatment were removed. Pruning of vines was continued until it stops vegetative growth. All field management practices like irrigation, weeding; fertilizer application, training, insect pest and diseases management were carried out uniformly as per the recommendation (Melese Asfaw, 2022). Odimeto 40% EC (Dimethoate 40% EC) at a rate of 1 liter per 200 L ha⁻¹ water was sprayed uniformly with fifteen days interval to control aphid (Melese Asfaw, 2022).

Watermelon should be harvested before vines become withered, and by understanding the maturity indicator of the fruit (Paltrinieri & Staff, FAO Retired, 2014). Several maturity

indicators (fruit colour, Tendrils or pigtails on vines, number of days from planting to maturity) help to determine when to harvest watermelons. Physiological maturity of first harvest of watermelon was collected if the fruit makes a sound when tapped by hands (Melese Asfaw, 2022).

3.4. Data Collection

Both vegetative and yield parameters were recorded during the field experiment. All parameters were collected from randomly taken five pre-tagged plants grown at the net plot area except 50% germination, 50% date of flowering and days to first harvest, which were determined on plot basis. Phenological, growth, yield and quality parameters of watermelon were collected following the standard procedures described below.

3.4.1. Phenological parameters

Days to 50% flowering: It was recorded by counting number of days elapsed from date of planting to date when 50% of the plants in the plot flowered.

Days to 1st harvest (Days): Days to 1st harvest was recorded by counting the number of days elapsed from date of planting to the date when at least two fruits per plot attend physiological maturity. Fruit of watermelon is physiologically matured when the fruit makes a sound when knocked with hand (Melese Asfaw, 2022).

Stand count at harvest: Stand count at harvest was recorded by counting the number of plants on each plot at final harvesting.

3.4.2. Growth parameters

Leaf area (cm²): It was recorded by measuring five leaves from the net plot at maturity. The selected five leaves were measured by leaf area meter and the average was taken. It was expressed in cm as total area of leaves produced per plant for each treatment and replication.

Stem height/ vine length (m): The vine lengths of five randomly taken plants were measured from the ground level to the tip of primary using meter scale at first harvest.

Number of lateral branches per vine: It was recorded by counting the number of lateral branch arisen from the main stem of five randomly taken and tagged plants at final harvest. The average number of lateral branches was computed and used for analysis.

3.4.3. Yield and yield related parameters

Number of fruits per plant: It was recorded by counting the fruits harvested from five randomly tagged plants grown in the net plot area. The average number of fruits per plant was computed and used for further analysis.

Marketable fruit yield (t/ha): Fruits which were free of diseases and insect pest damages were considered as marketable fruits (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022). Such fruits harvested from the net plot area were weighed using sensitive balance and expressed in $t\ ha^{-1}$.

Unmarketable fruit yield (%): Unmarketable yield was recorded by weighing fruits that were attacked by diseases and insect pests using scaled balance and expressed in percentage to the total fruit yield (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

Total fruit yield (t/ha): Total fruit yield was recorded by summation of marketable and unmarketable fruit yield.

3.4.4. Physico-chemical quality attributes

Average fruit weight (kg): The average weight of a fruit was recorded by weighing five fruits harvested from the net plot area at each harvest and dividing the weight to the number of fruits. The average fruit weight was computed and used for further analysis (Maggs-Kolling and Christiansen, 2003).

Fruit length (cm): The length of five randomly selected fruits that were taken from both first, second and final harvested from the net plot area was measured from the base to the tip of the fruit using meter scale. The average fruit length was computed and expressed in centimetre.

Fruit diameter (cm): The diameter of five fruits randomly taken from both first, second and final harvested from the net plot area was measured at the cross-section of sample fruits using meter scale. The average fruit diameter was computed and expressed in centimetre.

Fruit rind thickness (mm): Fruit rind thickness was recorded by cutting the cross-section of the fruit and measured the thickness in millimetre using Calliper meter. The average of five fruits were computed and expressed in millimetre.

Fruit size classification: Watermelons were grouped according to fruit size as icebox, mini, medium, large and very large. According to Wehner (2008) the fruit-size distribution of watermelon fruits are min <4, icebox 4.5–5, small 5.5–8, medium 8–10, large 11–14.5, and giant >14.5kg based on weight. Normal fruits were categorized into three groups in such a way that <4, 4.5–5, and 5.5–8 kg as mini, icebox, and medium fruits, respectively, and their percentile distribution was recorded eventually (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

Fruit chemical quality attributes

TSS (Total Soluble Solid): The totals soluble solid content was recorded by using a digital refractometer of five randomly selected fruits from the net plot at harvest. The fruits were grinded by Juice Gepper. TSS was measured by placing two drops of clear juice on the on the prism of refractometer and it's expressed in percentage (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

Juice content: Fruit juice was extracted from 1 kg of sliced fresh fruits were grinded by using Juice Geeper and the juice volume was measured by using a graduated cylinder. The averages of measured juices were expressed in millilitre of fruits.

Juice pH: Fruit juice was recorded randomly selected five fruits from the net plot at harvest. The harvested fruits were grinded by Juice Gepper and the juice was measured by pH meter (Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

3.5. Data Analysis

The data were subjected to two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS-9.4 statistical software package (SAS, 2008) following the standard procedure described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). In the presence of significant difference, mean separation was carried out using LSD method at 5% level of significance.

3.6. Partial Budget Analysis

The analysis of partial budget and marginal rate of return was done using the procedures described by CIMMYT (1988). The cost of vine pruning was considered as variable cost to

calculate the marginal rate of analysis. Costs which were similar to all treatments were considered as fixed costs and were not considered in partial budget analysis as described by CIMMYT (1988). For gross benefit determination, the prevailing local market price in the study area at the time of harvesting was taken (25-30 ETB Birr per kg). To calculate marginal rate of return, first the dominance analysis was carried out by listing the treatments in order of increasing the total variable costs. According to CIMMYT (1988) any treatments that have net benefits less or equal to the previous treatment was dominated and eliminated from further analysis. Marginal rate of return was calculated as a change of net benefit divided by change of cost in the treatment.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Effect of Sowing Date and Number of Vine on Phenology of Watermelon

4.1.1. Days to 50% of flowering

A day to 50% flowering was very highly significantly ($P < 0.001$) and significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the main effects of date of sowing and number of vine, respectively. However, the interaction effect had not significantly influenced ($P > 0.05$) days to 50% flowering of watermelon (Appendix Table 1).

The results showed that watermelon sown in January (51.5 days) was flowered earlier compared to November (59.75 days) and December (56.91 days) sown watermelon plants (Table 4.1). No differences in 50% flowering were observed between November and December sown watermelon plants. The difference in days to 50% flowering could be obviously associated with differences in temperatures between sowing dates, where the month January was relatively warmer compared to other sowing dates. Such warmer temperature facilitates growth and development of the crops and thus flowering of watermelon (Figure 3.2). Flowering in crops like watermelon is induced mainly by high temperatures (Bellad and Umesh, 2018). Similarly, the findings of Balkaya and Odabas (2007) revealed that November month recorded late flowering, fruit set and maturity than the month January.

Plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (52.88 days) and plants with four numbers of vines (55.11 days) took the shortest days to flowering, which statistically similar when compared each other. Plants with two (58.88) and three number of vines (57.33 days) required the longest days to flowering (Table 4.1). This change of flowering could be due to the up taking of nutrient computation between stems. The results of the present study are in agreement with the findings of Gholipouri and Nazarnejad (2007) who reported that pruned watermelon plants extend the time for flowering, fruit maturity and ripening, because after pruning each fruit need to more time for dry matter accumulation.

4.1.2. Days to 1st harvest

The analysis of variance showed that main effects of sowing date had very highly significantly ($P < 0.001$) and number of vines significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced days to first harvest. However, the interaction effect of sowing date and number of vines did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influence days to first harvest (Appendix Table 2).

Plants sown in January were earlier compared to December and November (Table 4.1). This might be due to the differences in temperature and other environmental conditions prevailed during the sowing times (Figure 3.2). These results are in agreement with Balkaya and Odabas (2007) who reported that sowing in month November recorded late flowering, fruit set and maturity which may be associated with fluctuating temperatures and high humidity and shorter sunshine hours that prolonged maturity of the crop.

Plants grown freely without vine pruning took the shortest (109.88) days to reach the first harvest compared to plants with two (117.11) and three (115.00) vines (Table 4.1). The results of the present study are in line with Gholipouri and Nazarnejad (2007) who reported that pruned watermelon plants extend the time for fruit maturity and ripening, which need more time to use dry matter accumulation of the plant.

4.1.3. Stand count at final harvest

The analysis of variance showed that date of sowing had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on average number of plant at harvest (Appendix Table 3). However, the main effect of number of vine and its interaction with date of sowing did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influences the average number of plant at harvest.

The result indicated that the highest number of plants at harvest was recorded from January (19.83) sowing followed by December (18.66) while, the lowest population was recorded from November (16.16) sowing (Table 4.1). This might be due to environmental factors. As it was observed, plants sown in November were affected by frost compared to January and December sowing (Figure 2.3). In agreement with these findings Bellad and Umesh (2018) also reported that November sowing was recorded the smallest number of plants as compared to January, and December sowing months.

Table 4.1: Main effects of date of sowing and number of vine on phenological parameters of watermelon

Sowing Date	Parameters		
	50% Flowering	Days to first harvest	Stand count at harvest
November	59.75 ^a	118.25 ^a	16.16 ^c
December	56.91 ^a	115.08 ^a	18.66 ^b
January	51.50 ^b	108.58 ^b	19.83 ^a
P-values	***	***	***
LSD(0.05)	3.62	3.93	0.76
Number of vine			
Without pruning	52.88 ^b	109.88 ^b	18.44
Two vine	58.88 ^a	117.11 ^a	18.33
Three vine	57.33 ^a	115.00 ^a	18.11
Four vine	55.11 ^{ab}	113.88 ^{ab}	18.00
P-values	*	*	ns
LSD(0.05)	4.18	4.54	0.87
CV (%)	7.66	4.09	5.25
SE±	0.59	0.64	0.13

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); ** = highly significant ($P < 0.01$); *** = very highly significance ($P < 0.001$); and ns = non-significant; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.2. Effect of Sowing Date and Number of Vine on Growth parameters of Watermelon

4.2.1. Leaf area

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of sowing date and number of vines had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on average leaf area of watermelon. However, the interaction effect of the factors did not significantly influence this parameter (Appendix Table 4).

Significantly the highest leaf area was recorded from November and January sowing compared to November sowing (Table 4.3). The difference in leaf area could be obviously associated with differences in temperatures between sowing dates, where the month January was relatively warmer compared to other sowing dates. Such warmer temperature facilitates growth and development of the crops (Figure 3.2). The results of the present study are in agreement with that of Mtumtum (2012) who stated that watermelon growth is more rapid during the dry season than during the wet season plants. Similar results are also confirmed by different authors (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007; Chandrashekhar, 2008).

Plants with two number of vine was recorded the highest leaf area (58.87 cm²) followed by plants with three vines while the lowest was recorded from un-pruned (52.18 cm²) plants (Table 4.3). Pruned watermelon plants had more leaf area than plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning). Pruning reduces competition for growth factors including nutrients, water; sunlight and space that intern improve the vegetative growth of individual plants as indicated in the present study. The results of the present study are in line with other scholars who reported that pruned watermelon plants produced the longest vine, leaf area and number of leaves, flowers and fruits per plant (Weiner and Freckleton, 2010, Oga and Umekwe, 2016).

4.2.2. Number of lateral branch per vine

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date and number of vines had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on number of lateral branch per vine of watermelon. Similarly, the interaction effect of these factors had significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced the average number of lateral branch per vine of watermelon (Appendix Table 5). In the main effect, January sowing increased lateral branches per vine compared to other sowing dates. Similarly watermelon plants with two vines recorded the highest number of lateral branches per vine.

In the interaction effect, the highest number of lateral branch per vine was recorded from plants that were sown in the month January with two vines (3.70). On the other hand, the lowest number of lateral branch per vine was recorded from un-pruned plants sown in all sowing dates (1.83) of watermelon (Table 4.2). The lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume, growth and plant vigour and finally the higher yield as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. The results of the present study clearly showed that

pruning had much higher effects on number of lateral branches per vine compared to date of sowing. The results are in harmony with the findings of other researchers who reported the increase of lateral branches by pruning (Kermani *et al.*, 2014; Bellad and Umesh, 2016).

Table 4.2: The interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine on lateral branch per vine of watermelon

Sowing Date	No of vine			
	Without pruning	Two vine	Three vine	Four vine
November	1.83 ^e	3.33 ^{abc}	2.60 ^d	2.00 ^e
December	1.90 ^e	3.60 ^{ab}	3.03 ^{bcd}	1.63 ^e
January	1.96 ^e	3.70 ^a	3.40 ^{abc}	3.00 ^{cd}
P- value			*	
LSD(0.05)			0.57	
CV (%)			12.70	
SE±			0.04	

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.2.3. Vine length

The analysis of variance showed that sowing dates had highly significant ($P < 0.01$) and number of vine had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on vine length of watermelon. However, vine length of watermelon was not influenced by the interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine (Appendix Table 6).

Accordingly, the plants sown in January was recorded the longest vine (2.62m) than the month December (2.38 m) and November (2.30 m) as indicated in Table 4.3. Whereas, the vines sown in month of November was small compared to January months which might be due to fluctuating cool weather, very low light and temperature, high humidity and shorter sunshine hours often coupled with unseasonal rains compared to those sown during the month January (Figure 3.2). These results of the present study are in line with Bellad and Umesh (2018) who stated that the plants sown in January month recorded the highest leaf area, vine length and lateral branches per vine than November month.

The longest vine per plant was recorded from plants with two vines (2.94 m) and three vines (2.77 m) while the lowest was without pruning (Table 4.3). The vine lengths of plants with two and three vines were statistically similar. Vine length of pruned plant was higher than plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning). This might be due to stiff competition of plants for growing resources including nutrients, moisture, and spaces, which in turn reduces the length of vine per plant. These results of the present study are in line with Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) who reported that the longest length of vine was recorded at the lowest plant density, whereas the smallest length of vine per plant was recorded at the highest plant population.

Table 4.3: Main effects of date of sowing and number of vine on growth parameters of watermelon

Sowing Date	Parameters		
	LA (cm ²)	NoLB/V	VL (m)
November	52.53 ^b	2.44 ^b	2.30 ^b
December	55.55 ^{ab}	2.54 ^b	2.38 ^b
January	57.28 ^a	3.01 ^a	2.62 ^a
P-values	*	***	**
LSD(0.05)	3.45	0.28	0.16
Number of vine			
Without pruning	52.18 ^b	1.90 ^c	1.81 ^c
Two vine	58.87 ^a	3.54 ^a	2.94 ^a
Three vine	55.54 ^{ab}	3.01 ^b	2.77 ^a
Four vine	53.87 ^b	2.21 ^c	2.21 ^b
P-values	*	***	***
LSD(0.05)	3.93	0.32	0.19
CV (%)	7.43	12.70	8.02
SE±	0.56	0.04	0.02

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); ** = highly significant ($P < 0.01$); *** = very highly significance ($P < 0.001$); and ns = non-significant; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LA = leaf area; NoLB/V = number of lateral branch per vine; VL = vine length; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.3. Yield and Yield Components of Watermelon

4.3.1. Number of fruit per vine

The analysis of variance revealed that date of sowing and number of vines had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on the number of fruits per vine of watermelon. However, number of fruits per vine of watermelon was not influenced by the interaction effect of date of sowing and number of vine (Appendix Table 7).

The highest number of fruit per vine of watermelon was obtained from January (1.48) date of sowing. On the other hand, the lowest number of fruits per vine of watermelon was obtained from November (1.11) sowing (Table 4.5). The difference in the number of fruit per vine of watermelon among the sowing dates might be due to differences in environmental conditions associated with the different sowing months (Figure 3.2). The results are in agreement with the results of Mtumtum (2012) who reported that Watermelon yields more fruit when planted at the dry season than during the wet season.

The highest number of fruits per vine of watermelon was obtained from plants with two vines (1.76) while, the lowest number of fruit per vine was recorded from un-pruned (0.77) plants (Table 4.5). This difference in the number of fruits per vine could be due to high competition among stems for growth factors including nutrient, sunlight, and space between stems. The lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume, growth and vigour and finally the higher yield as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. These results are in consistence with the findings of Gholipouri and Nazarnejad (2007) who reported that pruned watermelon produced more fruits per vine.

4.3.2. Number of fruit per plant

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date and number of vine had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on number of fruit per plant of watermelon. Similarly, the interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine per plant had significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced average number of fruits per plant of watermelon (Appendix Table 8). In the main effect, January date of sowing was increased number of fruits per plant compared to other sowing dates. Similarly watermelon plants with three vines recorded the highest number of fruits per plant than plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning).

In the interaction effect, the highest number of fruits per plant was obtained from treatment combination of January sowing and three number of vines (3.73) whereas, the smallest number of fruits per plant was recorded from November (2.51) and December (2.56) sowing combined with un-pruned plants (Table 4.4) This could be attributed to differences in environmental factors like that of temperature (Figure 3.2). These results are in consistent with Kermani *et al.* (2014) and Bellad and Umesh (2016) who reported that number of fruit was higher for plants grown at month January with stem pruned plants whereas; the smallest numbers were recorded at the combination of November sowing and plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning).

4.3.3. Marketable fruit yield

The analysis of variance showed that date of sowing and number of vine had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on marketable yield of watermelon. However, marketable yield of watermelon was not influenced by the interaction effects of sowing date and vine pruning (Appendix Table 9).

The higher marketable yield was recorded from plants sown in the month January (45.70 t ha^{-1}). On the other hand, the lowest fruit yield was obtained from November (26.87 t ha^{-1}) sowing (Table 4.5). The difference in the marketable yield of watermelon among the sowing dates might be due to poor growth and reproductive performances in view of fluctuating cool humid climate and very low night temperature backed by unseasonal rains during the month November (Figure 3.2). The results are in consistence with the findings of Balkaya and Odabas (2007), Chandrashekhar (2008) who reported that November sowing recorded the lowest marketable fruit yield per vine and hectare than January sowing.

Three number of vine was recorded the highest marketable fruit yield (42.15 t ha^{-1}) followed by two number of vines compared to the plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (31.06 t ha^{-1}) as indicated in Table 4.5. But, three numbers of vines and two numbers of vines recorded statistically similar marketable yields (42.15 t ha^{-1}) and (38.61 t ha^{-1}) respectively. This might be due to competition between vines for growing resources. The lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume and plant vigour and finally the higher yield as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. The results of the present study are similar with Gomes *et al.* (2019) who reported that the lower yield recorded on watermelon

plants without pruning could result from competition for water, nutrients and light (Gomes *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, Munoz-Rengifo *et al.* (2018) argued that since watermelon has naturally many branches, pruning is advised to keep adequate number of branches, leaves and fruits to enable them to share efficiently the plant resources.

4.3.4. Unmarketable fruit yield

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date and number of vine had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on unmarketable fruit yield of watermelon. Similarly, the interaction effect of sowing date and number of vines had significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced unmarketable fruit yield of watermelon (Appendix Table 10). In the main effect, November planting date was recorded highly unmarketable fruit yield than January planting in the present study. Similarly, plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning) were highly unmarketable fruit yield than pruned plants.

The highest percentage of unmarketable fruit yield was obtained from plants sown in the month November (12.16%) and plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning) whereas, the lowest was recorded from plants sown at the month January having two and three number of vines (4.16%) and (4.56%) respectively (Table 4.4). But, plants sown in the month of January with three and two numbers of vines were recorded statistically a similar unmarketable yields. This could be attributed to the differences in environmental factors due to differences in sowing date (Figure 3.2). The lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume and plant vigour and finally the higher yield as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. These results are in agreement with the findings of different researchers (Kermani Poorbaghaiy *et al.*, 2014; Maboko *et al.*, 2011; Bellad and Umesh, 2018; Rafaella *et al.*, 2018) who reported that plants sown at November season with un-pruned cucurbit plants produced higher un-marketable fruit yield than January sowing with pruned plants.

Table 4.4: The interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine on number of fruit per plant and unmarketable fruit yield of watermelon

Sowing Date	Number of vine	Parameters	
		Fruit per plant	Unmarketable fruit yield (%)
November	Without pruning	2.51 ^d	12.16 ^a
	Two vines	2.60 ^d	6.53 ^f
	Three vines	3.06 ^{bc}	7.96 ^{de}
	Four vines	2.83 ^{cd}	9.50 ^{bc}
December	Without pruning	2.56 ^d	10.06 ^b
	Two vine	3.20 ^b	6.83 ^{ef}
	Three vine	3.25 ^b	6.80 ^{ef}
	Four vine	3.13 ^{bc}	6.36 ^f
January	Without pruning	3.23 ^b	8.30 ^{cd}
	Two vine	3.63 ^a	4.16 ^g
	Three vine	3.73 ^a	4.56 ^g
	Four vine	3.15 ^{bc}	5.06 ^g
P- value		*	*
LSD (0.05)		0.33	1.22
CV (%)		9.35	9.84
SE±		0.02	0.10

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.3.5. Total fruit yield

The analysis of variance showed that date of sowing and number of vine had very highly significant ($p < 0.001$) effect on total yield of watermelon. However, the two factors did not interact to influence the average number of total yield of watermelon (Appendix Table 11).

The highest total fruit yield of watermelon was obtained from plants sown at the January (48.82 t ha⁻¹) date of sowing while; the lowest total fruit yield of watermelon was obtained

from November (29.48 t ha^{-1}) sowing (Table 4.5). The difference in total fruit yield of watermelon among the sowing dates might be due to environmental factors and sowing month (Figure 3.2). Which is in agreement with the results of Mutton (2012) who reported that watermelon plants grown in the dry season have recorded high yield than those sowing in wet season, which is also in agreement with other research findings (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007; Chandrashekhar, 2008).

In the case of number of vines the highest fruit yield) of watermelon was obtained from plants with three numbers of vines (44.95 t ha^{-1}) while, the lowest fruit yields were recorded from the plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (34.45 t ha^{-1}) and four number of vines (36.37 t ha^{-1}) as indicated Table 4.5. This difference in fruit yield of watermelon could be due to high competition among stems for growth factors including nutrient, sunlight, and space. The lower the number of vine per plant, the higher the root volume and plant vigour and finally the higher fruit quality as a result of improved nutrient and water uptake. These results are in consistence with the findings of Kahan (2013) who reported that high input management practices like pruning in watermelon produce greater marketable yield, higher number of marketable fruit/plant and higher fruit weight than low input management practices.

Table 4.5: Main effects of date of sowing and number of vine on yield and yield components of watermelon

Sowing Date	Parameters				
	NoF/V	NoF/P	MY (t ha ⁻¹)	UnMY (%)	TY (t ha ⁻¹)
November	1.11 ^c	2.75 ^c	26.87 ^c	8.85 ^a	29.48 ^c
December	1.30 ^b	3.03 ^b	36.79 ^b	7.42 ^b	39.74 ^b
January	1.48 ^a	3.43 ^a	45.70 ^a	6.39 ^c	48.82 ^a
P-values	***	***	**	***	***
LSD(0.05)	0.13	0.16	3.26	0.61	3.46
Number of vine					
Without pruning	0.77 ^d	2.77 ^c	31.06 ^b	9.84 ^a	34.45 ^c
Two vine	1.76 ^a	3.14 ^b	38.61 ^a	5.69 ^c	40.94 ^b
Three vine	1.55 ^b	3.35 ^a	42.15 ^a	6.22 ^{bc}	44.95 ^a
Four vine	1.11 ^c	3.03 ^b	33.99 ^b	6.54 ^b	36.37 ^c
P-values	***	***	***	***	***
LSD(0.05)	0.15	0.19	3.77	0.71	3.99
CV (%)	12.21	6.52	10.63	9.86	10.43
SE±	0.02	0.02	0.53	0.09	0.56

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); ** = highly significant ($P < 0.01$); *** = very highly significance ($P < 0.001$); and ns = non-significant; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; NoF/V = number of fruit per vine; NoF/P = number of fruit per plant; MY = marketable yield; UnMY = unmarketable yield; TY = total yield; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.4. Fruit Size Distribution and Physico-chemical Quality Attributes of Fruits

4.4.1 Fruit size distribution of watermelon fruit

Mini sized fruit category (<4kg)

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date, number of vine and their interaction very highly significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced the mini sized fruit yield of watermelon (Appendix Table 12). In the main effect, November planting date produced the highest

percentage of mini sized fruits compared to January sowing. On the other hand, un-pruned plants were the highest percentage of mini sized fruits than those plants from pruned plants.

The highest mini sized fruit yield percentage of watermelon were obtained from the treatment combination of November (66.60%), December (68.56%) and January (67.53%) sowings with plants where all the vines were allowed to grow while, the lowest mini sized fruit yield percentage (5.28 t ha⁻¹) was obtained from the combination of January sowing with two number of vines as indicated in Table 4.6. Generally, mini sized fruit percentage of plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning) was higher than pruned plants. The change of mini sized fruits might be due to different date of sowing and up taking of nutrient computation between stems. The difference among vine pruning in terms of mini sized fruit yield is in agreement with Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) who reported that high marketable fruits obtained from the highest plant density were mini in size, which might be less preferred by consumers. However, Tigist (2016) reported that fruits less than 3 kg are mostly preferable by local markets due to high cost of big watermelon.

Icebox sized fruit category (4.5-5kg)

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date and number of vines had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on icebox sized fruit yield of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*Number of Vine) had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influences on the icebox fruit sized yield of watermelon (Appendix Table 13).

The highest icebox fruit sized percentage yield (20.41%) was obtained from plants sown in the month January whereas the lowest icebox fruit sized percentage yields (19.15%) was recorded from the November sown watermelon (Table 4.8). The observed highest icebox fruit sized percentage yield of January sowing might be due to different date of sowing and environmental factors. The results of the present study are in line with the findings of Balkaya and Odabas (2007) who reported that physical quality parameters like fruit sizes are smaller in November sowing.

The highest icebox fruit sized percentage yield (22.40%) was recorded from three number of vines obtained by pruning activities performed, while the lowest icebox fruit sized percentage yield (18.14%) was recorded from plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (Table

4.7). The icebox sized fruit percentage yields of two vines (19.03%), four vines (19.23%) and control plants (18.14%) were statistically similar. The observed highest icebox fruit sized percentage yield of three vine plants might be due to management activities like that of pruning. The results of the present study are inconsistent with (Kahan, 2013) who reported that high input management practices in watermelon produce higher fruit size than low input management practices. This icebox sized fruits obtained from three numbers of vines were good quality and highly preferred by consumers. Besides to this, according to Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) who reported that as the inconvenience in handling big fruits, fruits in the range of 4.5–5.5 kg are highly preferred by consumers having small family size. With the same respect, (Zhou, 2011) reported that consumers having low incomes prefer small-to-medium-sized fruits rather than large fruits because of their high prices.

Small sized fruit category (5.5-8kg)

The analysis of variance showed that sowing date and number of vine had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on small sized fruit yield of watermelon. Similarly, the interaction effect (Sowing date*number of vine had highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) influences on small sized fruit yield of watermelon (Appendix Table 14). In the main effect, January planting time produced the highest percentage of small sized fruits compared to November planting. On the other hand, watermelon plants from pruned vines produced the highest percentage of small sized fruits than those plants from plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning).

The highest percentage of small sized fruit yield of watermelon was obtained from January sowing with two number of vines (22.40%) while the lowest percentage of small sized fruit yield was obtained from the combination of November (13.86%), December (14.00%) and January (14.80%) sowing with plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning), which are statistically similar as indicated in Table 4.6. This difference of small sized fruit percentage might be associated with sowing date, environmental factors and resource competition between vines (Figure 3.2). The results are in agreement with Davis *et al.* (2008); Leskovar *et al.* (2004) who reported that good management practices of pruning and training improves fruit size and quality. Similarly, (Zhou, 2011) reported that consumers having low incomes prefer small-to-medium-sized fruits rather than large fruits because of their high prices.

Table 4.6: The interaction effect of sowing date and number of vine on mini and small fruit sized category of watermelon

		Parameters	
Sowing Date	Number of vine	Mini fruit size (%)	Small fruit size
November	Without pruning	67.53 ^a	13.86 ^h
	Two vines	51.60 ^d	30.73 ^c
	Three vines	54.66 ^c	24.16 ^{de}
	Four vines	61.43 ^b	19.20 ^g
December	Without pruning	68.56 ^a	19.20 ^g
	Two vine	45.50 ^e	14.00 ^h
	Three vine	54.26 ^c	34.56 ^b
	Four vine	59.66 ^b	22.93 ^{ef}
January	Without pruning	66.60 ^a	14.80 ^h
	Two vine	41.90 ^f	37.50 ^a
	Three vine	51.63 ^d	25.13 ^d
	Four vine	55.93 ^c	23.93 ^{def}
P- value		***	**
LSD (0.05)		2.12	1.90
CV (%)		2.22	4.78
SE±		0.17	0.15

Where; ** = highly significant ($P < 0.05$); *** = very highly significant ($P < 0.05$); means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; LSD = least significant difference; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.4.2. Physical quality parameters

Fruit weight

The analysis of variance showed that the main effect of sowing date had highly significant ($P < 0.01$) effect and number of vine had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on average fruit weight of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*number of vine)

had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influence the average fruit weight of watermelon (Appendix table 15).

The heaviest fruit weight of watermelon was obtained from plants sown in the month January (3.63 kg) whereas, the smallest fruit weights were recorded from plants sown in the months November (3.22 kg) and December (3.28 kg), which were statistically similar when compared to each other (Table 4.7). The observed heaviest fruit weight might be due to relatively higher temperature in the month January which enhances the growth and development of the plants that in turn increases the weight of fruit (Figure 3.2). The results are in agreement with Balkaya and Odabas (2007) who reported that physical quality parameters like the fruit weights are heaviest on plants sown in the month in January followed by December and November sowing.

The heaviest average fruit weight was recorded from two numbers of vines (3.73 kg) by pruning activity, while the smallest average fruit weight was recorded from un-pruned (2.85 kg) plants (Table 4.7). The observed bigger average fruit weight from plants two vine plants might be due less competition for resources between the vines and less shading effect that enhance the photosynthesis activities. These results are in agreement with the findings of Pereira *et al.* (2011) who reported that the highest fruit weight were obtained at the lowest plant density, which was associated with less self-shading effect and highest light interception of photosynthesis.

Fruit length

The analysis of variance revealed that sowing date had a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect and number of vine had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on fruit length of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*Number of vine) had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influences on the average fruit length of watermelon fruits (Appendix Table 16).

The highest fruit length of watermelon fruit was recorded from January (17.91 cm) sowing whereas, the lowest fruit lengths were obtained from December (16.69 cm) and November (16.39 cm) date of sowings (Table 4.7). But, the average fruit length of December and November sowing dates were statistically similar. This change of fruit length might be due to sowing date and environmental factors (Figure 3.2). The difference among date of sowing in

terms of fruit length could be associated with Balkaya and Odabas (2007) who reported that physical quality parameters like the average fruit weight, specific gravity, fruit width and fruit rind thickness higher in January sowing followed by the February sowing but they were less in the November sowing.

The highest fruit length watermelon fruit was obtained from two (18.03 cm) and three number of vines (18.50 cm) whereas, the lowest fruit lengths and were recorded from four numbers of vine (16.28 cm) and plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (15.07 cm) (Table 4.7). The average fruit length of two number of vine and three numbers of vines were statistically similar. The observed fruit length of watermelon fruit among number of vine might be due to the up taking of nutrient computation between stems. This result of the present study line with Pereira *et al.* (2011) the highest fruit physical quality attributes that were obtained at the lowest plant density could be probably due to less self-shading that leads to maximum light interception of photosynthesis.

Fruit width

The analysis of variance revealed that sowing date had a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect and number of vine had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on fruit width of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*Number of vine) had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influences on the average fruit width of watermelon fruits (Appendix Table 17).

The highest fruit width was recorded from January sowing (16.91 cm) whereas, the lowest fruit widths and were obtained from November (15.45 cm) and December (15.61 cm) sowing dates (Table 4.7). But, the fruit width of November and December sowing dates were statistically similar. This difference among sowing date in terms of fruit width might be due to date of difference date of sowing and environmental factors (Figure 3.2). This result of the present study are associated with (Balkaya and Odabas (2007) reported that physical quality parameters like the average fruit weight, specific gravity, fruit width and fruit rind thickness higher in January sowing followed by the December sowing but they were less in the November sowing.

The highest fruit of watermelon fruit was recorded from two (17.50 cm) and three number of vines (17.10 cm). Whereas, the lowest fruit widths of watermelon fruits were obtained from

four numbers of vines (15.08 cm) and plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (14.28 cm) as indicated in Table 4.7. This is might be due to the up taking of resource computation between stems. This difference among vine pruning in terms of fruit width associated with Pereira *et al.* (2011) who reported that the highest fruit physical quality attributes that were obtained at the lowest plant density could be probably due to less self-shading that leads to maximum light interception of photosynthesis.

Rind thickness

The analysis of variance revealed that sowing date had highly significant ($P < 0.01$) effect and vine number had very highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on fruit rind thickness of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*Number of Vine) had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influences on the average fruit rind thickness of watermelon fruits (Appendix Table 18).

Accordingly, the highest fruit rind thickness of watermelon fruit was obtained from January (1.35 cm) sowing whereas; the lowest fruit rind thicknesses were recorded from November (1.21 cm) and December (1.22 cm) sowing (Table 4.7). But, the average fruit rind thicknesses of both December and November sowings were statistically similar. Generally, January sowing date was higher fruit rind thickness than December and November sowing. This difference among sowing date in terms of fruit rind thickness might be due to using of different sowing date and environmental factors (Figure 3.2). This result of the present study line with Mtumtum (2012) reported that Watermelon growth is more yielder and good quality during the dry season than during the wet season plants.

The highest fruit rind thickness of watermelon was recorded from two number of vine (1.35 cm) whereas; the lowest fruit rind thickness was obtained from plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (1.13 cm) plants (Table 4.7). Generally, pruned plant of watermelon fruits were higher fruit rind thickness than plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning). This difference among vine pruning in terms of fruit rind thickness might be due to the up taking of resource computation between stems. This result of the present study in agreement with Pereira *et al.* (2011) who reported that the highest fruit physical quality attributes that were obtained at the lowest plant density could be probably due to less self-shading that leads to maximum light interception of photosynthesis.

Table 4.7: Main effects of date of sowing and number of vine on physical quality attributes of watermelon

	Parameters						
	Mini (%)	Icebox (%)	Small (%)	AFW (kg)	FL (cm)	FW	FRT (cm)
Sowing Date							
November	58.80 ^a	19.15 ^b	21.99 ^c	3.22 ^b	16.39 ^b	15.45 ^b	1.21 ^b
December	57.00 ^b	19.58 ^{ab}	23.42 ^b	3.28 ^b	16.69 ^b	15.61 ^b	1.22 ^b
January	54.01 ^c	20.41 ^a	25.34 ^a	3.63 ^a	17.91 ^a	16.91 ^a	1.35 ^a
P-values	***	*	***	**	*	*	**
LSD(0.05)	1.06	1.08	0.95	0.25	1.18	1.13	0.08
Number of vine							
Without pruning	67.56 ^a	18.14 ^b	14.22 ^d	2.85 ^c	15.17 ^b	14.28 ^b	1.13 ^c
Two vine	46.33 ^d	19.08 ^b	34.26 ^a	3.73 ^a	18.50 ^a	17.50 ^a	1.35 ^a
Three vine	53.52 ^c	22.40 ^a	24.07 ^b	3.64 ^a	18.03 ^a	17.10 ^a	1.33 ^{ab}
Four vine	59.01 ^b	19.23 ^b	21.77 ^c	3.30 ^b	16.28 ^b	15.08 ^b	1.23 ^{bc}
P-values	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
LSD(0.05)	1.22	1.24	1.09	0.29	1.37	1.31	0.10
CV (%)	2.22	6.50	4.78	8.85	8.29	8.45	8.23
SE±	0.17	0.17	0.15	0.04	0.19	0.18	0.01

Where; * = Significant ($P < 0.05$); ** = highly significant ($P < 0.01$); *** = very highly significance ($P < 0.001$); and ns = non-significant; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different; Mini = mini-sized fruit category; Icebox = icebox sized fruit category; Small = small-sized fruit category; AFW = average fruit weight; FL = fruit length; FW = fruit width; FRT = fruit rind thickness; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.4.3. Chemical quality attributes of watermelon fruit

Juice content

The analysis of variance showed that the main as well as the interaction effects of sowing date and number of vine did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced the juice content of watermelon (Appendix Table 19). The juice contents of fruits sown at different sowing dates and the number of vines were presented in Table 4.8. The juice content of fruits from plants

sown at different sowing date ranged from 989.08 to 991.08 ml/kg. Similarly, the juice contents of fruits obtained from plants with different number of vines were ranged from 989.22 to 990.55 ml/kg which were statistically similar. The results are in line with the findings of Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) who reported that location and season did not affect the juice content.

Total soluble solid (TSS)

The analysis of variance showed that date of sowing and number of vine had very highly significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on total soluble solid (TSS) of watermelon. However, the interaction effect (Sowing date*Number of vine) had not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced the average value of total soluble solid (Appendix Table 20).

The plants sown at the month January (9.90 %) recorded the highest value of total soluble solid. The lowest total soluble solid was recorded from November (9.30 %) sown plants as indicated in Table 4.8. This change of total soluble solid at January sowing might be due to prevalence of congenial dry weather, bright sunshine cool humidity, moderately high light and temperature prevailed during grand vegetative growth period (Figure 3.2). These results are in agreement with the findings of other workers (Balkaya and Odabas, 2007; Bellad and Umesh, 2018). Similarly, Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) reported that TSS was influenced by watermelon production season.

The highest value of total soluble solid was recorded from two vines (9.88 %) of pruned plant; whereas, the lowest value of total soluble solid was recorded from the plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (9.15 %) as indicated in Table 4.8. The total soluble solid value of pruned plant was higher than plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning). This might be due to the shading effect of the plants at the plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning), which reduces the photosynthesis activities that in turn reduces the sugar content and thus TSS percentage. These results are in agreement with the findings of Watson (2002) who observed an inverse relationship between sugar concentration and level of shading. Similarly, Ford (2007) also reported that fruits harvested from watermelon plants with two vines had more TSS than those fruits harvested from watermelon plants with four vines. Sweetness in watermelon is also associated with the TSS concentration (Maynard *et al.*, 2002; Cheng *et al.*, 2016).

Juice pH

The ANOVA showed that main effects of sowing date and number of vines and their interaction had no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on juice pH (Appendix Table 21). The juice pH of fruits sown at different sowing dates and with different vine number was about 6.06 (Table 4.8). This result of the present study in agreement with Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2021) who stated that location and season did not affect all the tested fruit chemical quality parameters including juice pH.

Table 4.8: Main effects of date of sowing and number of vine on chemical quality attributes of watermelon fruit

Sowing Date	Parameters		
	JC (ml/kg)	TSS (%)	pH
November	989.91 ^a	9.30 ^b	6.06 ^a
December	989.08 ^a	9.33 ^b	6.06 ^a
January	991.08 ^a	9.90 ^a	6.06 ^a
P-values	Ns	***	Ns
LSD(0.05)	8.66	0.25	0.05
Number of vine			
Without pruning	989.22 ^a	9.15 ^c	6.06 ^a
Two vine	990.33 ^a	9.88 ^a	6.06 ^a
Three vine	990.55 ^a	9.64 ^{ab}	6.06 ^a
Four vine	990.00 ^a	9.35 ^{bc}	6.06 ^a
P-values	Ns	***	ns
LSD(0.05)	10.01	4.54	0.87
CV (%)	1.03	3.18	1.13
SE±	1.42	0.04	0.009

Where; *** = very highly significance ($P < 0.001$); and ns = non-significant; means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different JC = juice content; TSS= total soluble solid; pH = juice pH; CV = coefficient of variation; and SE± = standard error.

4.5. Economic Analysis of Watermelon as Influenced by Date of Sowing and Number of Vine

4.5.1. Partial budget analysis

According to CIMMYT (1988) the partial budget analysis includes the total variable costs and net benefits of each treatment. The gross benefit of the treatments was calculated using the adjusted yield and the field price of the crops while the net benefit was calculated by subtracting variable costs from the gross benefit of each treatment. In the present study, the pruning work to maintain the prescribed vine number was considered as variable cost which was done every week (800 Birr per month). Labour costs for fertilizer application, irrigation and seed costs were constant for all treatments, which were not considered in partial budget analysis. Moreover the marketable watermelon fruit yield was downscaled by 10% to make comparable to yields of farmers. The price of the fruit was obtained from watermelon producers and retailers in *Merawi* city, which is the nearest market to the study area.

According to the procedures described by CIMMYT (1988), the highest net benefit was obtained from plants sown in the month January and pruned with three vines with the value of 1,121,616.00 Birr ha⁻¹. On the other hand, the lowest net benefit was recorded from treatment combination of November sowing and plants where all the vines were allowed to grow (without pruning) with the value of 440,250.00 Birr ha⁻¹ (Table 4.9).

Table 4.9: Variable cost and gross incomes of watermelon as influenced by date of sowing and number of vine

Sowing Date	Number of vine	Pruning cost (Eth-Birr)	Marketable Yield (t tha ⁻¹)	AdY (t ha ⁻¹)	Gross income (Eth-Birr/ha)	Net benefit (Eth-Birr/ha)
November	Without pruning	-	22.86	20.57	440,250.00	440,250.00
	Two vines	52,528	28.91	26.01	692,763.00	640,235.00
	Three vines	35,464	32.91	26.61	693,616.00	658,152.00
	Four vines	22,240	22.79	20.51	478,460.00	456,220.00
December	Without pruning	-	30.42	27.37	684,250.00	684,250.00
	Two vine	56,530	40.05	36.04	876,768.00	820,238.00
	Three vine	54,648	42.33	38.09	952,250.00	897,602.00
	Four vine	30,384	34.38	30.94	768,420.00	738,036.00
January	Without pruning	-	39.90	35.91	718,200.00	718,200.00
	Two vine	65,872	46.88	42.19	1,068,094.00	1,002,222.00
	Three vine	72,015	51.21	46.08	1,193,631.00	1,121,616.00
	Four vine	64,660	44.80	40.32	1,050,420.00	985,760.00

Note: price of watermelon fruit = 25 and 30 Eth-Birr kg⁻¹; pruning and irrigation labour for one person = 1600 birr per month (i.e. pruning labour for one person = 800 birr per month); AdY = Adjusted Yield

4.6.2. Marginal rate of return

Marginal rate of return was calculated as a change of net benefit divided by change of cost in the treatment. Marginal analysis compares the net benefits with the total variable cost. The total variable cost was determined for each treatment and was compared with the net benefit. Dominance analysis was conducted by arranging the treatments ascending order of the variable costs and the corresponding net benefits. According to CIMMYT (1988) any treatments that have net benefits less or equal to the previous treatment was denominated and eliminated from further analysis (Table 4.10). Accordingly, sowing in the month January combined with three number of vine was recorded the highest marginal rate of return (1,943.57%) while the treatment combination of December sowing with four number of vine was recorded the lowest MRR (58.04%) as indicated in Table 4.11.

Table 4.10: Dominance analysis of watermelon as influenced by date of sowing and number of vine

Treatment combinations	Total variable cost (Birr ha ⁻¹)	Net benefit (Birr ha ⁻¹)	Dominance Analysis
January x Without Pruning	0	718,200.00	
November x Four vine	22,240	456,220.00	DO
December x Four vine	30,384	738,036.00	
November x Three vine	35,464	658,152.00	DO
November x Two vine	52,528	640,235.00	DO
December x Three vine	54,648	897,602.00	
December x Two vine	56,530	820,238.00	DO
January x Four vine	64,660	985,760.00	
January x Two vine	65,872	1,002,222.00	
January x Three vine	72,015	1,121,616.00	

Notes: DO = Dominance

Table 4.11: Marginal rate of return (MRR %) of watermelon as influenced by date of sowing and number of vine

Treatment combinations	Total variable cost (Birr ha ⁻¹)	Net benefit (Birr ha ⁻¹)	MRR (%)	Rank
January x Without Pruning	0	718,200.00		
December x Four vine	30,384	738,036.00	65.28	5
December x Three vine	54,648	897,602.00	657.62	4
January x Four vine	64,660	985,760.00	880.52	3
January x Two vine	65,872	1,002,222.00	1358.25	2
January x Three vine	72,015	1,121,616.00	1943.57	1

Notes: MRR = Marginal rate of return;

Chapter 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusions

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of sowing date and number of vine on growth, yield and quality of watermelon and to suggest the possible option for improving productivity. The results of the present study showed that sowing dates and number of vine determination in their main effects influenced almost all the tested phonological, growth, yield and quality parameters of watermelon. In their interaction effect, watermelon parameters including lateral branch per vine, number of fruit per plant, mini sized fruit category, small sized fruit category and unmarketable fruit yields were influenced by date of sowing and number of vine. Plants without pruning were inferior in all the tested parameters of watermelon. Decreasing the number of vines from four to two stems, also increase the parameters like lateral branch per vine, vine length, fruit per vine and total soluble solid. The temperature of January date of sowing was warmer than November, this warmer temperature increases growth and development of the plant finally increases yield and quality of the fruit. Moreover, significantly maximum marketable tuber yields of watermelon were obtained from seeds sown at January date and maintained three number of vines per plant with the values of (45.7 t ha⁻¹) and (42.15 t ha⁻¹) respectively. Based on the partial budget analysis, the treatment combination of January sowing and three vine numbers recorded the highest net benefits (1,121,616.00 Birr ha⁻¹) and marginal rate of returns (1,943.57%) respectively.

5.2. Recommendation

Sowing of watermelon in the month January and maintaining three vines per plants recorded the highest marketable yield and better fruit quality of watermelon, which can be recommended for economical production of the crop in the study area and areas with similar agro ecologies. Further similar researches on multi-location and seasons are also recommended.

REFERENCES

- Abebaw Abiyu and Tena Alamirew. 2015. Assessment of stage-wise deficit furrow irrigation application on maize production at Koga irrigation scheme, Blue Nile River Basin, Ethiopia. *Assessment*, 6(21): 21-29.
- Alao F.O., Adebayo T.A. and Olaniran O.A. 2016. Population density of insect pests associated with watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb) in southern guinea savanna zone, Ogbomoso. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 4(4).257-260.
- Alebachew Enyew, Dires Tewabe and Amare Tsige. 2020. Determining the irrigation regime of watermelon at Koga and Rib irrigation schemes in Amhara Region, Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 6(1). 1730108.
- Amsalu Ayana, Victor Afari-Sefa, Bezabih Emanu, Fekadu F. Dinssa, Tesfaye Balemi and Milkessa Temesgen. 2014. Analysis of Vegetable Seed Systems and Implications for Vegetable Development in the Humid Tropics of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 4(4):325-337.
- Anonymous. 2011. Production guidelines: Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*). Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries, Pretoria, Republic of South Africa.
- Anwar N.A., Gad A.A., Bardisi A. and Zyada H.G. 2019 Effect of plant spacing and apical shoot pinching on growth and productivity of watermelon plants under sandy soil conditions. *Zagazig J. Agric. Res.* 46(2): 357 365.
- Ara N., Bashar M.K., Begum S. and Kakon S.S. 2007. Effect of spacing and stem pruning on the growth and yield of tomato. *International Journal of Sustainable Crop Production*, 2(3): 35-39.
- Bahari M., Rafii M.Y., Saleh G.B. and Latif M.A. 2012. Combining ability analysis in complete diallel cross of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakai). *The Scientific World Journal*, 2012.
- Balkaya A. and Odabas M.S. 2007. The effects of sowing dates on seed yield and quality of red podded bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) cultivars. *Acta Horti* 729 :151-155.
- Bellad S. B. and Umesh H. 2018. Effect of Sowing Date, Spacing and Fertilizer Levels on Crop Growth and Seed Yield of Hybrid Watermelon. *Environment and Ecology*, 36(2), 498-507.
- Boualem A., Lemhemdi A., Sari M.A., Pignoly S., Troadec C., Abou Choucha F., Solmaz I., Sari N., Dogimont C. and Bendahmane A. 2016. The andromonoecious sex determination gene predates the separation of *Cucumis* and *Citrullus* genera. *PLoS one*, 11(5). 0155444.
- Brown A.C. and Summers W.L. 1985. Carbohydrate accumulation and colour development in watermelon. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* 110: 683–686.

- Chandrashekhar S. S. 2008. Seed technological studies in French bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*). PhD thesis. Univ AgricSci, Dharwad, Karnataka, India.
- Charles F.A. 2005. Watermelon breeder. Cucurbit Breeding Horticultural Science Retrieved.
- Cheng Y., Luan, F., Wang X., Gao P., Zhu Z., Liu S., Baloch A.M. and Zhang Y. 2016. Construction of a genetic linkage map of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) using CAPS and SSR markers and QTL analysis for fruit quality traits. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 202: 25-31.
- Chogou S.K., Assogba R., Degbey H., Abokini E. and Achigan-Dako E.G. 2019. Market structure and performance of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) in Benin. *Scientific African*, 3. 00048.
- CIMMYT (International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center). 1988. *From agronomic Data to Farmer Recommendations; An Economics Training Manual*. Completely revised edition. Mexico, D.F, no.27.
- Dauda S.N., Ajayi F.A. and Ndor E. 2008. Growth and yield of water melon (*Citrullus lanatus*) as affected by poultry manure application. *J. Agric. Soc. Sci.* 4(3): 121-124.
- Davis A.R., Webber C.L., Perkins-Veazie P., Ruso V., Lopez-Galarza S.A.L.V.A.D.O.R., Sakata Y.O.S.H.I.T.E.R.U. and Pitrat M. 2008. A review of production systems on watermelon quality.
- Ding P. and Syazwani S. 2009. Effect of Different Fruit Positions on Postharvest Quality of Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*). Enhancing plant productivity and ecosystem services and ecosystem services in a challenging environment in a challenging environment. 24:58.
- Dires Tewabe, Atakltie Abebe, Alebachew Enyew and Amare Tsige. 2020. Determination of bed width on raised bed irrigation technique of wheat at Koga and Rib irrigation projects, North West, Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture* (just-accepted), 1712767.
- Dittmar P.J., Schultheis J.R. and Monks D.W. 2006. Characterization of diploid watermelon pollenizers and utilization for optimal triploid watermelon production and effects of Halosulfuron POST and POST-DIR on Watermelon. MSc. Thesis. North Carolina State Univ.
- Dube J., Ddamulira G. and Maphosa M. 2021. Watermelon production in Africa: challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Vegetable Science*, 27(3): 211-219.
- Elmstrom G.W. and Davis P.L. 1981. Sugars in developing and mature fruits of several watermelon cultivars. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* 106: 330–333.
- Eve B., M. Tuarira and M. Moses. 2016. The influence of pinching on the growth, flowering pattern and yield of butternuts (*Cucurbita moschata*). *Int. J. Hort. and Ornamental Plants*, 2 (1): 19-25.
- Fanos Mekonnen. 2014. Agriculture of ASSP Project in Ethiopia. Watermelon Fruit Production under irrigation in Oromia.

- FAO. Watermelon Crop Information. 2019. Available from: <http://www.fao.org/land-water/databases-and-software/crop-information/watermelon/en/>.
- Gbotto A.A., Koffi K.K., Tro H.H., Baudoin J.P. and B.I. 2016. Morphological diversity in oleaginous watermelon (*Citrullus mucosospermus*) from the Nangui Abrogoua University germplasm collection. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 15(21): 917-929.
- Gholipouri A. and Nazarnejad H. 2007. The effect of stem pruning and nitrogen levels of on some physico-chemical characteristics of pumpkin seed (*Cucurbita pepo* L.). *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences: PJBS*, 10(20): 3726-3729.
- Gichimu B.M., B.O. Owuor G.N. Mwai and M.M. Dida. 2009. Morphological characterization of some wild and cultivated watermelon (*Citrullus* sp.) accession in Kenya. *ARN J. Agric. Biol. Sci.*, 4: 1990- 6145.
- Gichimu B.M., Owuor B.O. and Dida M.M. 2008. Agronomic performance of three most popular commercial watermelon cultivars in Kenya as compared to one newly introduced cultivar and one local landrace grown on dystric.
- Gomes R.F., Santos L.D.S., Braz L.T., Andrade F.L. and Monteiro S.M. 2019. Number of stems and plant density in mini watermelon grown in a protected environment. *Pesq. Agropec. Trop.*, 49: 54196: 18.
- Gomez K.A. and Gomez A.A. 1984. *Statistical Procedures for Agricultural Research*. 2nd Ed., John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York: 328-332.
- Gusmini G. and Wehner T.C. 2006. Qualitative inheritance of rind pattern and flesh color in watermelon. *Journal of Heredity* 97: 177–185.
- Gusmini, G., and T.C. Wehner. 2005. Foundations of yield improvement in watermelon. *Crop Sci.* 45:141-146.
- Habtamu Tegen, Melkamu Alemayehu, Getachew Alemayehu, Ermias Abate and Tadele Amare. 2021. Response of watermelon growth, yield, and quality to plant density and variety in Northwest Ethiopia. *Open Agriculture*, 6(1): 655-672.
- Habtamu Tegen, Melkamu Alemayehu, Getachew Alemayehu, Ermias Abate and Tadele Amare. 2022. Bridging the attainable yield gaps of watermelon through nitrogen and phosphorus nutrients management in North-West Ethiopia. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 45(1): 69-85.
- Huitron-Ramirez M.V., M. Ricardez-Salinas F. and Camacho Ferre. 2009. Influence of grafted watermelon plant density on yield and quality in soil infested with melon necrotic spot virus. *HortScience* 44:1838-1841.
- Kassa Ashebre. 2015. Opportunities and Potential in Ethiopia for Production of Fruits and Vegetables: A Graduate Senior Seminar Paper. *African Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7 (6): 328-336.

- Ke S. K., Ding M., Li L., Niu Q. L. and Huang, D. F. 2012. Grafting watermelon seedling production management system based on process control strategy. *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University (Science)*, 17(2): 129-134.
- Kermani Poorbaghaiy S.A., Pouryousef M., Jamshidi K. and Azimi M.R. 2014. Effects of plant density and main stem pruning on yield and its components of pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* con var. *pepo* var. *styriaca*). *Iranian Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants Research*, 30(1): 1-9.
- Kuvare U.S. 2005. *Greenhouse production of watermelon (Citrullus lanatus)* (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University).
- Lamprey S. and Koomson E. 2021. The Role of staking and pruning methods on yield and profitability of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) production in the Guinea Savanna Zone of Ghana. *Advances in Agriculture*, 2021.
- Leskovar D.I., Bang K.M. Crosby N. Maness J.A. Franco and P. Perkins-Veazie. 2004. Lycopene, carbohydrates, ascorbic acid and yield components of diploid and triploid watermelon cultivars are affected by deficit irrigation. *J. Hortic. Sci. Biotechnol.* 79(1): 75–81.
- Loukou A.L., Gnakri D., Djè Y., Kippré A.V., Malice M., Baudoin J.P. and B.I. 2007. Macronutrient composition of three cucurbit species cultivated for seed consumption in Côte d'Ivoire. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.*, 6: 529-533.
- Maboko M.M., Du Plooy C.P. and Chiloane S. 2011. Effect of plant population, fruit and stem pruning on yield and quality of hydroponically grown tomato. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 6(22): 5144-5148.
- Maggs-Kölling G. L. and J. L. Christiansen. 2003. Variability in Namibian landraces of watermelon (*Citrullus Lanatus*). *Euphytica* 132 (3): 251–58.
- Maggs-Kölling G.L., Madsen S. and Christiansen J.L. 2000. A phenetic analysis of morphological variation in *Citrullus lanatus* in Namibia. *Genet. Resour. Crop Evol.*, 47: 385-393.
- Mandel H.N., Levy S., Izkovitch S. H. and Korman. 2005. "Elevated plasma citrulline and arginine due to consumption of *Citrullus vulgaris* (watermelon)." *Journal of inherited metabolic disease* 28, no. 4: 467-472.
- Masika, F.B., Alicai, T., Shimelis, H., Ddamulira, G., Athman, S.Y., Ipulet, P., Andama, M. and Tugume, A.K., 2022. Pumpkin and watermelon production constraints and management practices in Uganda. *CABI Agriculture and Bioscience*, 3(1): 39
- Mayberry K.S., Hartz T.K., and Valenzia J. 2008. *Watermelon Production in California*. Vegetable Research and Information Center. University of California.
- Maynard D. 2001. Watermelons: characteristics production and marketing ASHS press Nigeria, *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 3: 325-330.

- Maynard D.N., Dunlap A.M. and Sidoti B.J. 2002. Sweetness in diploid and triploid watermelon fruit. *Report-Cucurbit Genetics Cooperative*, 25: 32-35.
- Melese Asfaw . 2022. Review on Watermelon Production and Nutritional Value in Ethiopia. *J Nutr Sci Res* 7: 173.
- Melkamu Alemayehu, Fentahun Tessafa, Solomon Bizuayehu, Belayneh Ayele. 2015. *Amhara region horticulture development strategy* (ARHDS) (2015-2019). Prepared by College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Bahir Dar University. Bahir Dar, Ethiopia.
- Melkamu Alemayehu and Minwelet Jemberie. 2018. Optimum rates of NPS fertilizer application for economically profitable production of potato varieties at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwestern Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 4(1): 1439663.
- Merwade M.N. 2000. Investigation on seed production techniques and storability of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*L.). PhD thesis. Univ Agric Sci Dharwad, Karnataka, India.
- Minwelet Jemberie. 2017. Effects of NPS Fertilizer Rate and Irrigation Frequency Determination Method on the Growth and Tuber Yield of Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) in Koga Irrigation Scheme, West Gojjam, North Western Ethiopia (Doctoral dissertation, Bahir Dar University).
- Mtumtum N.P. 2012. *Performance of wild watermelon (Citrullus lanatus L.) in response to population density and mulch*. M.Sc. thesis, School of Agricultural, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, Zambia.
- Mujaju C., Zborowska A., Werlemark G., Garkava-Gustavsson L., Andersen S.B. and Nybom, H. 2011. Genetic diversity among and within watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) landraces in southern Africa. *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology*, 86(4): 353-358.
- Munozrengifo J., Villamartorres R., MolinavilLamar J., Cruzaty L.G., Navarrete B.T., Moncada B.C., Olaya J.C., Matute A.M., Ortégaguevara D., Jazayeri S.M., 2018. A correct combination of pruning, spacing and organic fertilizer improve development and quality of fruit in watermelon cultivar: case of Ecuadorian littoral. *Biosci. Res.*, 15(3): 14621471.
- Nanasato Y., Miyake C., Takahara K., Kohzuma K., Munekage Y.N., Yokota A. and Akashi K. 2010. Mechanisms of drought and high light stress tolerance studied in a xerophyte, *Citrullus lanatus* (wild watermelon). In *The Chloroplast*: 363-378.
- Nantoume A.D., Christiansen J.L., Andersen S.B. and Jensen B.D. 2012. On-farm yield potential of local seed watermelon landraces under heat-and drought-prone conditions in Mali. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 150(6): 665-674.
- Nascimento T.L.D., Souza F.D.F., Dias R.D.C.S. and Silva E.F.D. 2018. Agronomic characterization and heterosis in watermelon genotypes. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Tropical*, 48: 170-177.

- Nayak S.R., Parmar V.K., Patel A.N., Suchismita J., Lathiya J.B., Tandel Y.N., 2018 Efficacy of pinching and plant growth regulators in enhancing yield characters of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.). *Int. J. Chem. Stud.*, 6 (1): 1804-1807.
- NIHORT. 2000. National Horticultural Research Institute. 25 years of research into Horticultural Crops Development in Nigeria (1975 – 2000). A Commemorative Publication: 120-122.
- Oga I.O. and P.N. Umekwe. 2016. Effects of pruning and plant spacing on the growth and yield of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) in Unwana-Afikpo. *Int. J. Sci. Res.*, 5 (4): 110- 115.
- Paris H.S. 2015. Origin and Emergence of the Sweet Dessert Watermelon, *Citrullus lanatus*. *Annals of Botany*, 116: 133–148.
- Park Y. and Cho S. 2012. Watermelon production and breeding in South Korea. *Israel Journal of Plant Sciences*, 60(4): 415-423.
- Pereira F.A.D.L., Medeiros J.F.D., Gheyi H.R., Dias N.D.S., Preston W. and Vasconcelos, C.B. 2017. Tolerance of melon cultivars to irrigation water salinity. *Revista Brasileira de Engenharia Agrícola e Ambiental*, 21: 846-851.
- Pereira F.H.F., Puiatti M., Finger F.L. and Cecon P.R. 2011. Growth, assimilate partition and yield of melon charenthais under different shading screens. *Horticultura Brasileira*, 29: 91-97.
- Perkins-Veazie P. and Collins J.K. 2004. Flesh quality and lycopene stability of fresh-cut watermelon. *Postharvest Biology and Technology* 31: 159-166.
- Perkins-Veazie P., Davis A. and Collins J.K. 2012. Watermelon: from dessert to functional food. *Israel Journal of Plant Sciences* 60: 395-402.
- Rafaella M.D.A., Aroucha E.M., de Medeiros J.F., do Nascimento I.B. and de Paiva C.A. 2018. Effect of main stem pruning and fruit thinning on the postharvest conservation of melon. *R. Bras. Eng. Agríc. Ambiental*, 22(5): 355-359.
- Ravikumar G.H., Shekhar Gouda M., Vasudevan N., Basa-vegowda Mahadevareddy. 2005. Influence of spacing, nipping and fruit retention on seed yield and seed quality in cucumber. *Seed Res* 33: 82-87.
- Soteriou G.A., Kyriacou M.C., Siomos A.S. and Gerasopoulos D., 2014. Evolution of watermelon fruit physicochemical and phytochemical composition during ripening as affected by grafting. *Food Chemistry* 165: 282–289.
- Statistical Analysis System (SAS). 2008. Version 9.4. SAS Institute Inc. Cary, NC. USA.
- Suchoff David H., Jonathan R., Schultheis Christopher C., Gunter Richard L., Hassell Frank J. and Louws. 2019. "Effect of rootstock and nitrogen fertilizer on growth and yield in watermelon." *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology* 94, no. 6: 798-804.

- Susila T., Reddy S.A., Rajkumar M., Padmaja G. and Rao P.V. 2012. Effects of sowing date and spraying of brassinosteroid on yield and fruit quality characters of watermelon. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 8(3): 223-228.
- Thomas M., E. Demeulenaere J. C. and Dawson. 2012. On-farm dynamic management of genetic diversity: the impact of seed diffusions and seed saving practices on a population-variety of bread wheat, *Evolutionary Applications*, 5, 8, 779-795.
- Tigist S. 2016. Nutritional composition, anti-nutritional factors and antioxidant properties of different local varieties of watermelon fruit from around Koka, Ethiopia. *Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: Addis Ababa University*.
- Viana T.V., Alves A.M., Sousa V.F., Azevedo B.M., Furlan R.A., 2008. Planting density and number of drains influencing the productivity of rose plants cultivated in pots. *Hortic. Bras.*, 26(4): 528532.
- Walters S.A., Groninger J.W. and Myers Jr O. 2012. Rebuilding Afghanistan's agricultural economy: Vegetable production in Balkh province. *Outlook on AGRICULTURE*, 41(1): 7-13.
- Warncke D.D. 2007. Nutrient management for cucurbits: Melons, pumpkin, cucumber, and squash. Indiana CCA. Michigan State University. USA.
- Warren R., J. Duthie J. Edelson J. Shrefler and M. Taylor. 1998. Relationship between watermelon foliage and fruit. In: Proceedings of the 17th Ann. Hort. Industries Show, 229- 234. January 9-10.
- Watson R., Wright C.J., McBurney T., Taylor A.J. and Linforth R.S.T. 2002. Influence of harvest date and light integral on the development of strawberry flavour compounds. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 53(377): 2121-2129.
- Wehner T.C. 2008. Watermelon. In Prohens J, Nuez F (eds.) *Vegetables I. Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Chenopodiaceae, and Cucurbitaceae*. Springer Science Business Media, New York: 381-418.
- Wehner T.C. 2008. Watermelon. In *Vegetables I* Springer, New York, NY: 381-418.
- Weiner J. and Freckleton R.P. 2010. Constant final yield. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*: 173-192.
- Xu Y. Guo S. and Liu J. 2012. Dynamic characteristics of enzymes and transcriptome related to sugar metabolism and accumulation in sweet and non-sweet watermelon fruits. In: Sari N, Solmaz I, Aras V, eds. *Cucurbitaceae 2012, Proceedings of the Xth Eucarpia meeting on genetics and breeding of Cucurbitaceae*. Adana: Cukurova University, 103–111.
- Zhou W., 2011. *Demand for watermelon and application of AIDS models*. University of Florida.

APPENDICES

Appendix Table 1: ANOVA Table for days to 50% flowering

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	F- value	P – value
Rep	2	190.16	95.08	8.07	0.2456
Sowing Date	2	421.72	210.86	11.42	0.0003
Number of Vine	3	185.22	61.74	3.34	0.0360
Date*Number of Vine	6	13.61	2.26	0.12	0.9925
CV (%)	7.66				
R ² (%)	0.58				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 2: ANOVA Table for days to maturity or first harvest

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	247.38	123.69	9.86	0.0654
Sowing Date	2	582.88	291.44	13.37	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	248.30	82.76	3.80	0.0233
Date*Number of Vine	6	88.44	14.74	0.68	0.6702
CV (%)	4.09				
R ² (%)	0.63				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 3: ANOVA Table for stand count at harvest

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	4.22	2.11	2.61	0.0959
Sowing Date	2	84.22	42.11	45.94	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	1.111	0.37	0.40	0.7514
Date*Number of Vine	6	2.88	0.48	0.53	0.7835
CV (%)	5.25				
R ² (%)	0.80				

Where; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 4: ANOVA Table for leaf area

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	147.70	73.85	6.37	0.0666
Sowing Date	2	138.66	69.33	4.13	0.0287
Number of Vine	3	219.92	73.30	4.37	0.0137
Date*Number of Vine	6	10.75	1.79	0.11	0.9948
CV (%)	7.43				
R ² (%)	0.47				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 5: ANOVA Table for number of lateral branch per vine

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F-value	P- value
Rep	2	0.08	0.04	0.34	0.7181
Sowing Date	2	2.26	1.13	9.87	0.0007
Number of Vine	3	15.16	5.05	44.05	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	1.94	0.32	2.82	0.0319
CV (%)	12.70				
R ² (%)	0.87				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 6: ANOVA Table for vine length

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.23	0.11	3.70	0.0513
Sowing Date	2	0.68	0.34	8.88	0.0013
Number of Vine	3	7.32	2.44	63.75	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.22	0.03	0.99	0.4545
CV (%)	8.02				
R ² (%)	0.89				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 7: ANOVA Table for number of fruit per vine

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.42	0.21	25.84	0.0654
Sowing Date	2	0.81	0.40	16.11	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	5.33	1.77	70.08	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.25	0.04	1.68	0.1690
CV (%)	12.21				
R ² (%)	0.91				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 8: ANOVA Table for number of fruit per plant

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.04	0.02	0.57	0.5741
Sowing Date	2	2.82	1.41	35.06	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	1.56	0.52	12.89	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.64	0.10	2.68	0.0389
CV (%)	6.52				
R ² (%)	0.93				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 9: ANOVA Table for marketable fruit yield

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	35.36	17.68	1.20	0.3214
Sowing Date	2	2129.69	1064.84	72.02	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	650.23	216.74	14.66	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	31.38	5.23	0.35	0.9040
CV (%)	10.63				
R ² (%)	0.88				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 10: ANOVA Table for unmarketable fruit yield

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.82	0.41	0.78	0.4691
Sowing Date	2	74.63	37.31	70.70	0.0001
Vine pruning	3	100.99	33.66	63.77	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	9.718	1.61	3.07	0.0245
CV (%)	9.86				
R ² (%)	0.94				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 11: ANOVA Table for total fruit yield

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	34.50	17.25	1.03	0.3727
Sowing Date	2	2135.66	1067.83	63.91	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	599.78	199.92	11.97	0.0001
Sowing date*Number of Vine	6	36.32	6.05	0.36	0.894
CV (%)	10.43				
R ² (%)	0.88				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 12: ANOVA Table for mini sized fruit category

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	140.52	70.26	44.13	0.0687
Sowing Date	2	140.52	70.26	44.13	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	2168.62	722.87	454.00	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	73.14	12.19	7.66	0.0001
CV (%)	2.22				
R ² (%)	0.98				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 13: ANOVA Table for icebox sized fruit category

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	9.94	4.97	3.03	0.0673
Sowing Date	2	9.94	4.97	3.03	0.05
Number of Vine	3	92.69	30.89	18.80	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	14.80	2.46	1.50	0.2201
CV (%)	6.50				
R ² (%)	0.74				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 14: ANOVA Table for small fruit sized category

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	67.80	33.90	26.60	0.0654
Date	2	67.80	33.90	26.60	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	1847.41	615.80	483.20	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	44.51	7.41	5.82	0.0007
CV (%)	4.78				
R ² (%)	0.98				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 15: ANOVA Table for average fruit weight

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	1.19	0.59	6.67	0.0501
Sowing Date	2	1.19	0.59	6.67	0.005
Number of Vine	3	4.33	1.44	16.08	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.02	0.004	0.05	0.9994
CV (%)	8.85				
R ² (%)	0.72				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 16: ANOVA Table for fruit length

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F - value	P- value
Rep	2	15.66	7.83	3.94	0.0532
Sowing Date	2	15.66	7.83	3.94	0.0332
Number of Vine	3	64.29	21.43	10.78	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	1.74	0.29	0.15	0.9881
CV (%)	8.29				
R ² (%)	0.63				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 17: ANOVA Table for fruit width

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	15.47	7.73	4.23	0.2566
Sowing Date	2	15.47	7.73	4.23	0.0266
Number of Vine	3	64.96	21.65	11.85	0.0001
Date*Number of Vine	6	1.128	0.18	0.10	0.9953
CV (%)	8.45				
R ² (%)	0.65				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 18: ANOVA Table for fruit rind thickness

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.13	0.06	6.18	0.0680
Sowing Date	2	0.13	0.06	6.18	0.0068
Number of Vine	3	0.28	0.09	8.64	0.0005
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.0083	0.0013	0.13	0.9916
CV (%)	8.23				
R ² (%)	0.61				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 19: ANOVA Table for juice content

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	24.22	12.11	0.11	0.8924
Sowing Date	2	24.22	12.11	0.11	0.8924
Number of Vine	3	9.19	3.06	0.03	0.9932
Date*Number of Vine	6	62.88	10.48	0.10	0.9958
CV (%)	1.03				
R ² (%)	1.42				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 20: ANOVA Table for total soluble solid

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	2.72	1.36	14.88	0.0532
Sowing Date	2	2.72	1.36	14.88	0.0001
Number of Vine	3	2.80	0.93	10.18	0.0002
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.70	0.11	1.28	0.3014
CV (%)	3.18				
R ² (%)	0.73				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Table 21: ANOVA Table for fruit juice pH

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	F- value	P- value
Rep	2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.9959
Sowing Date	2	0.00003	0.00001	0.00	0.9959
Number of Vine	3	0.00005	0.00001	0.00	0.9997
Date*Number of Vine	6	0.00096	0.00016	0.03	0.9998
CV (%)	1.13				
R ² (%)	0.009				

Where; Df = Degree of freedom; SS = sum square; MS = mean square; CV = coefficient of variation; and R² = R- square

Appendix Figure 1: Seedling and pruning of the experiments, during 2021 growing season at Koga district

Appendix Figure 2: Partial view of growth performance and measure leaf area of the experiment, during 2022 growing season at Koga district

Appendix Figure 3: Harvested sample watermelon fruits, during 2022 growing season at Koga district

Appendix Figure 4: Partial view of some laboratory work and measure fruit physical quality parameters of the experiment, during 2022 growing season at Koga district

Appendix Figure 5: Partial view of some laboratory work and measure fruit chemical quality parameters of the experiment, during 2022 growing season at Koga district

BIOGRAPHICAL SCKETCH

The author, Yibeltal Tilahun, was born to his father Tilhun Ayele and his mother Birhan Nnega in Motta Town, East Gojjam Zone of Amhara National Regional state, Northern Ethiopia on May 15, 1994. He attended his elementary and junior secondary school at Tikil Dingay. After completing elementary education, he was enrolled at Sede Secondary and Motta Preparatory School and completed his Secondary Education in the year 2014. In 2015, he joined Debre Markos University College of Agriculture and Environmental Science graduated with BSc in Horticulture. In 2018, he was employed by Injibara University College of Agriculture, Food and Climate Science as chief technical assistance in the department of horticulture. In 2021 he joined the School of Graduate Study at Bahir Dar University College Agriculture and Environmental Sciences to pursue his M.Sc. degree in horticulture.